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Deliverable D3.1: ACHIEVE Self-Standing Modules: Market Analysis and Curriculum Design

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Deliverable D3.1: ACHIEVE Self-
Standing Modules: Market analysis and
curriculum design

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Abstract

Deliverable D 3.1 presents the design of the ACHIEVE self-standing learning modules, grounded in a comprehensive market needs analysis addressing current and emerging skill demands in Cloud Computing, Networking Infrastructure, and High-Performance Computing (HPC). The analysis combines qualitative inputs from industry and practitioner surveys with quantitative patent-based analysis to capture both immediate labour market requirements and forward-looking technological trends, with particular attention to areas characterised by rapid innovation and skills uncertainty.

The present deliverable draws on this evidence in order to define a structured and modular curriculum framework targeting professionals, job seekers, career changers, and lifelong learners seeking up-skilling and re-skilling opportunities. The proposed self-standing modules are designed to be flexible, stackable, and aligned with European skills frameworks, enabling scalable training pathways that complement the ACHIEVE master's programme while remaining accessible to a broader audience beyond traditional higher education.

The deliverable further outlines the initial design of certification schemes associated with the self-standing modules, detailing their structure, target audiences, learning outcomes, and assessment approaches. These certifications aim to provide recognisable and market-relevant credentials that support employability, professional mobility, and lifelong learning. Overall, Deliverable D3.1 contributes to SO1 – Addressing skill needs, by translating robust market intelligence into industry-aligned learning content and certification pathways that strengthen Europe's advanced digital skills ecosystem.

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Project Abstract

Advanced Cloud and High-Performance Infrastructure for European Education (ACHIEVE) aims to train the next generation of specialists and innovators in Cloud Computing, Networking Infrastructure (CNI), and High-Performance Computing (HPC) in Europe. ACHIEVE will reach this goal by designing and delivering a double-degree master's programme (ISCED Level 7, 120 ECTS) with a major in Cloud and Networking Infrastructure and a minor in Innovation and Entrepreneurship. The master's programme is designed and created by 8 higher education institutions from 6 different countries, together with leading research centres in HPC and EIT Digital, a pan-European organisation with long-standing expertise in delivering education programmes in advanced digital skills across Europe. ACHIEVE will foster strong interactions and mobility between academia and business, strengthen knowledge-triangle integration, promote entrepreneurship, foster inclusiveness, and boost the growth of the existing EIT Digital ecosystem, one of the largest digital ecosystems in Europe. In addition to the master's programme, ACHIEVE partners will develop and deploy self-standing learning modules on Cloud, Networking, and HPC topics. These modules will result in certifications in advanced digital skills released by participating higher education institutions and EIT Digital, targeting a wide audience of students and professionals. In line with the goals of the Digital Compass and the New European Innovation Agenda, ACHIEVE will train more than 1000 participants across four years and contribute to reducing the gap in advanced digital skills in Europe while increasing Europe's competitiveness in key digital technology domains such as Cloud, Networking, and HPC. Finally, it is important to highlight the added value of this project: while training opportunities in HPC, Cloud Computing or Networking exist in Europe, ACHIEVE is the 1st European double-degree master's programme that systematically integrates Cloud, Networking Infrastructure, and HPC with Innovation and Entrepreneurship, thereby addressing a crucial need for Europe's digital transformation.

Executive Summary

This document reports on the design phase of the ACHIEVE self-standing learning modules, focusing on:

- A short-term, labour-market-oriented needs analysis for Cloud, Networking, and High-Performance Computing (HPC);
- The definition of a curriculum for self-standing learning modules targeting professionals, job seekers, and individuals seeking up-skilling and re-skilling;
- The design of certification schemes aligned with identified needs.

This deliverable directly contributes to SO1 – Addressing skill needs, and supports the preparation of industry-relevant, flexible learning pathways complementary to the academic curricula addressed in Task 1.1.

In contrast to Task 1.1, which focuses primarily on students and long-term academic skills planning, Task 3.1 addresses (i) Professionals already active in the labour market (ii) Individuals requiring short-term skill acquisition, (iii) Job seekers aiming to improve employability in Cloud, Networking, and HPC domains.

The analysis therefore emphasizes current and emerging industry demands, rather than long-term disciplinary developments, in order to ensure that the proposed training programme addresses specific, short-term skills gaps identified in the sector. This approach has enabled the project to establish the definition of self-standing learning modules (SSLMs) based on evidence from feedback received from companies, market/literature analysis and, in the case of HPC, forward-looking indications derived from patent analysis. As a result, the design of ACHIEVE's training modules is not only aligned with existing professional practices but also geared towards the technological trajectories that will shape the future needs of the workforce.

1 Target Groups and Training Needs for SSLMs and Micro-Credentials

This section outlines the market analysis that was conducted in order to identify the demand for Self-Standing Learning Modules (SSLMs) and micro-credentials, as well as to define the target groups for this activity of the ACHIEVE project. It establishes the rationale for the design requirements that guide the development of modular and stackable learning pathways, which are aligned with European skills priorities.

The market analysis of self-standing learning modules and micro-credentials reveals demand to be segmented into four macro-categories of users. All of these categories are considered ACHIEVE target groups, although they vary in terms of their level of relevance and strategic focus.

1) Professionals undergoing upskilling/reskilling. This segment represents the core of the demand for micro-credentials. These are workers already in the labour market who need to update or retrain their skills in response to digital transformation, the green transition and the evolution of organisational models. Their participation is driven by the need for immediate applicability of knowledge and formal recognition of training outcomes. The centrality of this target group is motivated by its high potential volume, the strong interest of companies in continuing education solutions, and their willingness to invest in flexible programmes compatible with work activities.

2) Career changers. The second group includes adults who want to reposition themselves professionally in new sectors or roles. Unlike professionals who are simply updating their skills, they require more structured pathways that can facilitate a complete transition of skills and professional identity. The strategic importance of this segment stems from the increasing discontinuity of career paths and the need for training tools that bridge different disciplinary fields, capable of reducing the perceived risk of change.

3) New workers/students. This category includes university students, recent graduates and young people entering the job market. For these users, standalone modules complement formal training, helping them to acquire practical skills that are geared towards employability and aligned with the demands of businesses. This segment is particularly significant as it constitutes a pool of future professionals and influences the progressive integration between traditional education systems and micro-credentials.

4) Lifelong learners. The fourth target group includes people motivated by personal interests or by the need to update their skills, not strictly related to their career. Although it has less economic weight than the professional segments, it contributes to the cultural diffusion of continuous learning and broadens the user base of the designed modules, strengthening their long-term sustainability.

The identification of four target groups provides an integrated view of the learning demand that characterizes the market for self-standing learning modules. Despite the diversity of individual profiles and motivations, the market analysis highlighted the emergence of four cross-cutting training needs, which constitute the common design reference for micro-credentials. These needs represent the meeting point between user expectations and the requirements of companies, educational institutions, and all the other actors involved in skills development processes. They define, in a complementary manner, the conditions under which autonomous modules can be perceived as effective and credible tools for lifelong learning.

a) Short, modular courses. The increasing pressure of modern life and work schedules makes essential the provision of short and flexible training units that can be combined according to personal needs. While this need is particularly evident among professionals and lifelong learners, it affects all segments of society, as it reduces barriers to access and enables gradual progression in learning. Modularity is therefore a necessity for the real spread of training.

b) Structured courses with guided learning paths. Alongside flexibility, it is essential to provide guided learning paths that offer structure and direction,

enabling learners to navigate the modular offerings more effectively. These pathways transform a potentially fragmented set of courses into a coherent skills development trajectory by linking individual modules to recognisable professional profiles and concrete employment outcomes. This is particularly important for career changers and new workers, who need clear, progressive routes to build or reposition their professional identities.

c) Scalable training with standardization of skills. For training modules to have a real impact, it is essential that they are designed to be scalable, i.e. that they can be replicated across a large number of users, without any loss of quality. As an example, scalability enables companies to train large numbers of professionals quickly and uniformly, thereby supporting digital transformation processes and the continuous updating of skills. From this perspective, standardizing learning outcomes is an enabling tool as it allows micro-credentials to be integrated into HR, enabling the systematic monitoring of training outcomes or recruitment targets.

d) Recognizable certifications. The value of credentials is a cross-cutting element of the first three targets and represents the main mechanism for translating learning into employment advantages. In particular, the value of digital learning only becomes tangible when the outcomes can be translated into credible signals for the labour market. Recognised certifications are therefore a decisive factor for professionals, career changers, and students. They transform educational experience into spendable capital, promoting career progression, access to new roles and dialogue between educational and productive systems.

Together, these four requirements are the pillars on which the value proposition of the self-standing learning modules framework under development in ACHIEVE should be based.

The combination of the identified segments and the above-described needs justifies the choice of a modular and stackable offering model. Indeed, upskilling professionals favour modularity, standardization, and certification, while career changers prioritize guided learning paths and recognized

qualifications. Students and new workers require structured pathways to help them enter the job market, and lifelong learners value flexibility and accessibility above all other factors. This mapping confirms the relevance of the four target groups selected for the project's positioning strategy. The following table maps the four requirements against the identified target macro-categories of users, using three levels of relevance: Marginal (low), Relevant, and Core (high).

Table 1. Mapping between target macro-categories and requirements

	Requirements			
Target Macro-Categories	Short, modular courses	Guided learning paths	Scalable training with skills standardisation	Recognizable certifications
Professionals upskilling/reskilling	Core	Relevant	Core	Core
Career changers	Relevant	Core	Relevant	Core
New workers/students	Relevant	Core	Relevant	Core
Lifelong learners	Core	Relevant	Marginal	Marginal

The definition of target groups and requirements also meets the growing demand for transferable and technical specialist skills that can be updated through flexible learning pathways. It therefore responds to the priorities outlined in European policies on reskilling and employability. It is also consistent with the main European reference frameworks for skills and lifelong learning, particularly the European Qualifications Framework (EQF).

The European Qualifications Framework (EQF) will be used to define the level of autonomy, responsibility, and complexity of the learning outcomes. This alignment permits the ACHIEVE partners to translate technical content into credentials that are meaningful and understandable in the job market. The adoption of EQF descriptors allows the learning outcomes of individual

modules to be linked to recognised levels of competence and professional profiles at a European level.

2 Methodology for Market Needs Analysis

The market analysis aimed to identify current and emerging skill demands in Cloud, Networking, and HPC, by capturing both objective indicators of innovation and subjective needs expressed by practitioners.

Within the project, the training needs and market analysis was conducted using a differentiated methodological approach based on the degree of maturity of the technological areas covered by the project. For the Cloud and Networking infrastructures domains, it was deemed appropriate to rely on a combination of qualitative analysis of the results of the survey of companies, analysis of micro-credentials already present on the main international platforms, and a review of technical and industry literature. Although these areas are characterized by rapid technological evolution, they present a relatively consolidated skills framework, supported by widespread industry standards, already codified professional profiles, and a broad and structured training offer. In this context, the main objective was to align the new micro-credentials with existing best practices, avoiding complete duplication and creating a coherent learning path.

The situation was different in the High-Performance Computing (HPC) domain. As known at the beginning of the project and confirmed by the survey findings (see Section 3.1), it showed limited availability of specific training courses and greater uncertainty on the part of companies about the evolution of the skills required, particularly due to its rapid evolution in relation to the convergence between classical HPC, artificial intelligence, heterogeneous architectures, and quantum technologies. This scenario makes an analysis based exclusively on the existing offer less effective, as the latter only partially reflects the innovation trajectories currently underway.

For this reason, the qualitative analysis was conducted alongside an in-depth analysis of recent patent trends, with the aim of identifying early signs of technological development and future skills requirements. Patents are, in fact, a privileged source for identifying emerging directions that have not yet been fully translated into courses and certifications, allowing for the design of micro-credentials with a forward-looking and not merely adaptive perspective. This approach could make possible to identify innovative subject areas that could have been unlikely to emerge from an analysis limited to current training offerings.

The organisation of the following section reflects the methodological approach carried out within the project.

2.1 Qualitative Approach: Questionnaire-Based Analysis

To define the content of the SSLMs/micro credentials provided by the ACHIEVE project in an evidence-based manner, a Europe-wide survey was conducted, mainly between August and October 2025. The survey was designed with two objectives in mind: on the one hand, to understand the state of adoption of High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Cloud Computing in industry and academia; on the other, to identify in a structured way the skills requirements and desired characteristics for short, modular, and professional training courses.

The questionnaire was developed in coordination with the WPI activities dedicated to the design of the Master's program, but was supplemented with a section specifically focused on continuing and non-academic education, in particular micro credentials. This methodological choice responds to the growing European interest in flexible upskilling tools, also highlighted in the debate on attracting and retaining HPC talents in the context of the EuroHPC Summit.

The survey was mainly defined as a set of closed-ended questions that guarantees to receive a larger set of answers and to gather qualitative insights on gaps, priorities, and barriers. It was distributed through the ACHIEVE consortium partners, professional networks (including LinkedIn), and conferences, ensuring broad, multi-sector coverage. A total of 188 valid responses were collected from 21 European countries, with significant representation from the AI & Data Science, Biotechnology, and Healthcare & Pharmaceuticals sectors, consistent with the technological convergence dynamics between HPC, Cloud, AI, and Big Data also highlighted in industry analysis.

The nine questions most relevant to micro-credential/SSLMs design were:

- Q1. What is the size of your organization (based on full-time employees)?
- Q2. Which topics should an HPC/Cloud training program cover to support your industry's needs?
- Q3. What technical skills do you look for when hiring HPC/Cloud professionals?
- Q4. What are the biggest skill gaps you observe among new HPC/Cloud hires?
- Q5. What is your preferred method of HPC/Cloud training delivery?
- Q6. How important is it for employees to have industry-recognized HPC/Cloud certifications?
- Q7. Would your company encourage new employees to complete an HPC/Cloud certification program?
- Q8. Would your company fund HPC/Cloud certification or training for employees?
- Q9. What are the main barriers to upskilling employees in HPC/Cloud at your company?

Question Q1, relating to company size, was introduced to understand how company scale influences the ability to invest in training and the presence of structured internal skills. The needs of a micro-enterprise differ from those of

a large organization with dedicated IT teams. The analysis of Q1 allowed us to consider the calibration of micro-credentials in terms of duration, cost, modularity, and potential B2B offering, taking into account different training absorption capacities.

Question Q2 played a central role in defining the content. The aim of this question was to avoid an exclusively academic design of the modules, instead gathering direct information on the priorities perceived by the market. The answers to Q2 made it possible to distinguish between core skills (e.g., parallel programming, cluster management, HPC architectures) and sector-specific application skills, highlighting the need for modules that are potentially differentiated by industry domain.

Questions Q3 and Q4 were designed to complement each other. Q3 explored the technical skills desired during the hiring process, providing a clear indication of employability requirements. Q4, on the other hand, identified gaps observed in new hires, highlighting the misalignment between training offerings and actual needs. The cross-analysis of Q3 and Q4 was a key methodological element in designing SSLMs as targeted gap-filling tools, with learning outcomes directly linked to employment needs.

Question Q5, regarding preferred delivery methods, was formulated to ensure that SSLMs were compatible with work activities and lifelong learning models. The answers to Q5 provided valuable insights into preferences for online or blended formats, the importance of hands-on components, and the possible need for remote access to HPC infrastructure, all of which were key factors in the methodological design of the modules.

Questions Q6, Q7, and Q8 have been designed to explore the dimensions of certification and economic sustainability. In particular, Q6 investigates the value attributed to industry-recognized certifications; Q7 and Q8 verifies companies' willingness to encourage or finance such paths. This information is essential for assessing the positioning of ACHIEVE SSLMs within the European skills ecosystem and for exploring models of structured collaboration with the private sector.

Finally, Q9 addressed the issue of barriers to upskilling. Understanding the obstacles (such as time constraints, costs, and lack of targeted offers) is essential to designing SSLMs that could be realistically adopted. The evidence gathered through Q9 guides the design toward short, also practical modules that are potentially stackable and compatible with professional workloads.

In addition to these questions, we also included in our analysis a further question of the survey that was more open ended: “If you could recommend one HPC/Cloud-related course to be added to university programs, what would it be?”. With respect to the others, this has been left open with the goal of gather further insights not explicitly gathered form the others.

Overall, the integrated analysis of all designed questions (Q1-Q9) allows micro credentials to be defined not as a mere downscaling of the Master's program designed in WP1, but as distinct, modular tools geared towards having an immediate impact on employability. The methodology adopted permits the integration of academic and industrial perspectives, ensuring consistency with the dynamics of the European HPC and Cloud market.

2.2 Quantitative Approach: Patent-Based Market Analysis

As part of Task 3.1, a patent-based analysis was conducted to identify technological trends and emerging skill needs in High-Performance Computing (HPC) and related Cloud and Networking domains. The analysis adopts a quantitative, data-driven approach to complement traditional labour market studies and stakeholder surveys. Patent analysis provides an evidence-driven view of innovation activity, reflecting:

- Actual R&D investments,
- Industry priorities and technological convergence,

Emerging application areas before they are fully reflected in job descriptions or training programs.

Unlike surveys, patent data reveals what companies are actively developing, rather than what stakeholders believe they need ¹.

2.2.1 Data Collection

Lens.org was used to acquire relevant patents since its collection covers 94 countries and over 140 million patents, and it is free for limited data downloads. It also provides a valuable functionality for distinguishing between granted patents and patent applications, even when these are recorded by different patent offices in heterogeneous or non-standardized formats.

Patent Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC) and keywords were both used to retrieve relevant patents about the HPC technology. The search with CPC classification provides more accurate results about technology than a keyword search, since these codes are assigned and systematically controlled by field experts. However, CPC codes can be too general or narrow for the technology that is the subject of the search; some patents may be pending for CPC classification, and not all patents are classified according to CPC codes.

Keyword-based search was used to mitigate these risks, especially for patent applications. Therefore, keywords about HPC technologies were included in addition to the CPC codes for patent retrieval. The CPC subclass codes and keywords, which are given in Table 1, were used to retrieve the patents covering the years 2000-2024. A keyword search was conducted on the titles, abstracts, claims, and descriptions sections of the patents. 95,665 patent

¹ An article titled “Transformation of High-Performance Computing: A Large-Scale Patent Analysis Using BERTopic and Social Network Methods” which provides the details of this quantitative approach, has been submitted to the Scientometrics Journal.

documents were retrieved, including non-English patents. Non-English patents were translated by using the Python library “googletrans (v4.0.0rc1)”.

Table 2. CPC codes and keywords used to retrieve relevant patents

Search Strings	# of Results	Retrieval Date	
Title: "high performance computing" OR ("high performance computation" OR "high performance computer") OR Abstract: ("high performance computing" OR ("high performance computation" OR "high performance computer")) OR (claim: ("high performance computing" OR ("high performance computation" OR "high performance computer")) OR description: ("high performance computing" OR ("high performance computation" OR "high performance computer"))) Filters: regex = false, publishedDate.from = 2000-01-01, publishedDate.to = 2024-12-31	46,787	22 January 2025	
Title: supercomputing OR (supercomputation OR supercomputer) OR Abstract: (supercomputing OR (supercomputation OR supercomputer)) OR (claim: (supercomputing OR (supercomputation OR supercomputer)) OR description: (supercomputing OR (supercomputation OR supercomputer))) Filters: regex = false, publishedDate.from = 2000-01-01, publishedDate.to = 2024-12-31	48,878		
Total	95,665		
Post-Processing			
CPC SubClasses/Main Groups Filtering	G02B, G06F, G06N, G06T, H01L, H04L, H04N, H05K7, Y02D10		79,427
Granted Patents Filtering	Document Type = Granted Patents (2000-2024)		35,777
Imputation for the last two years	Document Type = Applications (2023-2024)		9,163
	After Filtering + Imputation	44,940	

After filtering granted patents with CPC codes and implementing imputations for the years 2023-2024 (i.e., patent applications were also included for these years without filtering), the final dataset included 44,940 patents. Imputation for the years 2023-2024 was necessary, since the application process may take

18-24 months. CPC code filtering is not applied to those patent applications since they may be pending for CPC classification.

On the final dataset, titles and abstracts were pre-processed for NLP analyses. The claim and description sections of the patents were not included in NLP analyses since their preamble parts cause noise, resulting in redundant emphasis on some topics. Punctuation, stopwords removal, and lemmatization were applied by using the “nltk (v3.7)” library of Python and WordNet lemmatizer. Tokenization was also applied by using the “nltk (v3.7)” library.

2.2.2 Topic Modelling

BERTopic model was chosen as the topic modelling method, after a rigorous comparative evaluation against the conventional LDAseq method. This comparison focused on topic quality metrics, the capacity to capture dynamic temporal behaviour, and qualitative analysis. This implementation utilized the “bertopic (0.16.2)” Python library.

Different cluster configurations of BERTopic were also evaluated. These results were qualitatively interpreted to identify the configuration that best reflected the HPC technology domain. To achieve greater topic granularity and accurately model dynamic behaviour, HDBSCAN (Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) clustering was utilized with a minimum topic size of 10, which generated 898 topics with coherence scores comparable to k-means, but with a naturally lower diversity score for later years. This decrease in diversity is expected when increasing the topic number, as related concepts (e.g., Virtualization of GPU resources, Quantization of ML models for GPUs, GPU-based parallel processing, etc.) result in more topics sharing common words.

2.2.3 Topic Labeling

Topic labelling was manually applied through a structured, six-step procedure given below to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and consistency across topics:

Step 1: Initial Keyword Interpretation

- Topic representations: words are scanned.
- Potential themes are identified (e.g., Terms such as 'affinity', 'isa', and 'delegate' reflect runtime behavioral analysis and instrumentation mechanisms in software systems.).

Step 2: Validate with Representative Documents

- Titles and abstracts of representative documents per topic are read.
- Whether the keywords reflect the document content is checked
- In the case of ambiguity, “Background” and “Prior Art” sections of representative patent documents are also read (e.g., does "flow" refer to airflow in a CFD simulation or dataflow in a processing pipeline).

Step 3: Anchor to HPC Context

- Whether the label fits within the scope of High-Performance Computing is checked:
 - Is it an HPC application (e.g., scientific simulation, ML training, transaction processing, etc.)?
 - Is it an HPC infrastructure or system component (e.g., interconnects, cooling sub-systems)?

Step 4: Label Construction

- Concise noun phrase structures are used to label topics.
- Combine core concept + domain context (e.g., "Authentication Systems" + "Quantum Entanglement" as "Quantum Entanglement-based Authentication Systems").
- General terms like "invention", "technology" are avoided unless they are central.

Step 5: Consistency Check

- Newly labeled topics are checked against existing ones in terms of naming conventions and context.

Step 6: Final Comparison against LLMs

- Topic labels are automatically generated for 898 topics by two different LLMs ("Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct" and "Qwen/Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct") with the following prompt:

"I have a topic described by the following keywords: [KEYWORDS]
The topic has the following representative patents:
[REPRESENTATIVE PATENTS]

Based on the information above, give a short label for the topic."

- Resulting labels are compared with the manual coding.

The LLM-generated labels were then compared with the manual coding, which confirmed a generally strong agreement. Divergences observed, such as those sampled in Table 3, primarily reflected differences in the level of granularity rather than contradictory interpretations.

Table 3. Samples from LLM triangulation

Topic Representation Words	Manual Labeling	Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct
['serviceable', 'weighted', 'entity', 'amount', 'queueing', 'underserved', 'queue', 'ensuring', 'proportion', 'quota', 'priority', 'available', 'issuing', 'become', 'greater']	Weighted Scheduling for System Resource Management	Weighted Workload-Based Scheduling System	Weighted Workload Scheduling
['migration', 'vm', 'migrated', 'batch', 'migrating', 'virtual', 'machine', 'containerized', 'virtualized', 'gmgd', 'live', 'bare', 'gang', 'destination', 'migrate']	Virtual Machine Migration Management	Virtual Machine Task Management System	Virtual Machine Migration Management
['ib', 'infiniband', 'subnet', 'fc', 'fabric', 'arp', 'gid', 'subnets', 'routing', 'guid', 'switch', 'lid', 'ip', 'port', 'manager']	Infiniband Network Management and Subnet Routing	Infiniband Network Management and Routing Architecture	InfiniBand Network Architecture
['quantum', 'classical', 'qpu', 'heterogeneous', 'preprocessor', 'variable', '300', 'randomized', 'plugin', 'processor', 'computing', 'unit', 'hybrid', 'program', 'classic']	Hybrid Quantum-Classical Computing Architecture	Quantum-Classical Hybrid Computing Architecture Design	Quantum-Classical Heterogeneous Computing
['alert', 'object', 'target', 'geolocation', 'detection', 'designated', 'specie', 'ai', 'intelligent', 'recognition', 'learned', 'timeframe', 'emission', 'following', 'delivering']	AI-based Intelligent Target Object Detection and Alert System	Intelligent Target Object Detection and Alert System	Intelligent Target Object Detection System

2.2.4 Dynamic Topic Modelling

For dynamic topic modelling, publication years of patents were used as an additional input. The original BERTopic Dynamic model represents topics per year with five words. A small modification was implemented to change the number of representative words. This enabled us to understand and label niche topics better and to make fair comparisons between different models.

BERTopic Dynamic model calculated the appearance/disappearance of the topics per year, which was then visualized by a scatter plot to identify emerging sub-technologies and applications of the HPC domain. The analysis resulted in the investigation of the 898 distinct topics across four time periods: topics that were present since 2000, topics that emerged after 2006, after 2012,

and after 2018. In this way, persistent topics and emerging topics could be identified.

2.2.5 Graph-theoretic Grouping of Topics

A patent-topic matrix was generated to create a two-mode network (i.e., bipartite network), defined by two distinct sets of nodes: patents and topics. Edges in this network exist exclusively between nodes of different sets and maps patents into one or more topics.

The two-mode patent-topic network was subsequently transformed into a one-mode network via network projection. This process collapses the patent node set by creating edges between topics that co-occur within the same patent. Thus, the resulting topic-topic network represents the relationships between topics, where nodes are the topics themselves and relationships are defined by their co-occurrence values in the patents. To focus the analysis on the most significant relationships, only the top fifth percentile of co-occurrence values (i.e., strong relationships) were included. Sum and max valued-core decompositions were performed on the topic-topic network to identify core topics of the HPC.

The identified core nodes were further segmented by applying the Louvain community detection algorithm.

In parallel with the network-topology-based valued core analysis, hierarchical clustering was also applied using the correlated Euclidean network-based dissimilarity distance.

While valued core analysis reveals localized topological clusters, hierarchical clustering helps identify foundational, motor, and niche themes within the HPC domain by capturing the global similarities between topics. A dendrogram was constructed to visualize the results of the hierarchical clustering.

2.3 Comparison of Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis Results

The two approaches were systematically compared to ensure robustness:

- Geographical differences:

Patent data is dominated by US-based innovation, while survey participants reflect a broader European profile.

- Domain coverage:

All domains mentioned in the questionnaire are covered by patent-derived priority modules.

- Emerging topics:

Patent analysis revealed additional high-growth domains (e.g., retail, entertainment, supply chain, quantum computing) not yet strongly visible in survey responses.

Overall, the comparison confirmed that patent-based prioritization fully encompasses practitioner-expressed needs, while also identifying future-critical skill areas.

3 Key Findings of the Market Needs Analysis

3.1 Questionnaire Analysis

The market analysis confirms a strong and growing demand for advanced skills in both High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Cloud technologies, while also revealing a persistent mismatch between existing educational provision and the competencies expected in real-world contexts. Across the survey responses, organizations describe not only a shortage of professionals, but also a gap in the type of preparation available: learners often possess solid theoretical foundations, yet need stronger capacity to apply knowledge in hybrid, data-intensive, and innovation-driven environments.

This finding is particularly relevant for ACHIEVE. The survey evidence should not be interpreted only as a request for narrowly employer-specific training, but more broadly as a signal that the European skills ecosystem requires flexible learning pathways that connect foundational knowledge, emerging technologies, and applied problem-solving. This applies both to company-oriented upskilling and to re-skilling and lifelong learning audiences, whose needs may differ in immediacy but converge around flexibility, recognizability, and progressive competence development.

3.1.1 Topics Identified from the Questionnaire

The survey shows that organizations are looking for professionals who can work across HPC and Cloud ecosystems and navigate not only technical components, but also broader operational and governance considerations. As reflected in the results summarized in Figure 1 and Figure 2, respondents identify parallel programming, GPU acceleration, HPC-Cloud interoperability, DevOps for scientific computing, cloud orchestration, and application

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development among the most important technical skills for current and future professionals.

These results indicate that the market increasingly values hybrid competence profiles. In other words, employers are not simply asking for specialists in isolated technologies, but for individuals able to understand how infrastructures, applications, and workflows interact across environments. This includes, in many cases, awareness of data governance, security compliance, and cost-efficient resource management, which appear as complementary competencies in the broader skill profile expected from learners entering these fields.

Figure 1. Most important technical skills for HPC professionals, according to the ACHIEVE survey

Figure 2. Most important technical skills for cloud professionals, according to the ACHIEVE survey

At the same time, respondents repeatedly note that traditional programmes provide a valuable theoretical base but do not always sufficiently prepare learners for the complexity of modern interdisciplinary workflows. For ACHIEVE, this point is highly relevant, but it should be translated into an educational response that is compatible with the project’s university-based and online delivery model.

Rather than attempting to replicate industry training environments in full, the implications for ACHIEVE are better framed in terms of an applied, problem-oriented, and scenario-based educational approach. The survey findings point to the need to strengthen learners’ ability to interpret architectures, reason across workflows, and transfer knowledge to realistic contexts, but this does not necessarily require full access to industry-grade operational platforms. In fact, this is an area where ACHIEVE can provide distinctive value through university-based SSLMs: by combining conceptual depth, innovation-oriented content, and structured learning around emerging architectures, workflows, and computational paradigms, the modules can prepare learners for

advanced computing practice in ways that complement, rather than duplicate, vendor- or platform-specific training.

Looking more specific to the set of topics demanded by the survey respondents, they are illustrated in Figure 3. As shown in the figure, participants expect training to cover core Cloud and HPC concepts, with particular attention to technologies and tools relevant for the use and operation of HPC systems in organizational settings. At the same time, the responses indicate a clear interest in innovation-oriented topics that go beyond introductory coverage. These results are especially important for ACHIEVE, because they confirm that the expected educational offer should not be limited to foundational digital skills, but should also include forward-looking content aligned with technological evolution.

The inclusion of such topics in ACHIEVE SSLMs is therefore not only justified by academic and research trends but directly supported by market evidence from the questionnaire.

Figure 3. HPC Training Program Topic Demands (Q: Which topics should an HPC training program cover to support your industry’s needs?)

Finally, when analyzing the responses to the open-ended question, “If you could recommend one HPC/Cloud-related course to be added to university programs, what would it be?”, it is important to consider that, unlike the other questionnaire items, this question was less guided and therefore more directly shaped by the respondents’ background and application domains. In this context, 65% of the answers recommended topics related to HPC/Cloud applications (mainly HPC applications). This result appears consistent with the profile of the participants and their sectoral focus (e.g., Bio, Pharma and Cheminformatics, Geoscience, CFD), where the primary need is often the effective use of Cloud and HPC systems rather than the development of Cloud and HPC infrastructures themselves. These indications will be taken into account in the design of the ACHIEVE modules, in particular by incorporating

application-oriented examples and use cases that reflect the domains represented in the survey.

Beyond topic coverage, the responses also confirm the increasing convergence of HPC and Cloud in practice. The survey indicates that a substantial share of organizations rely on both HPC and Cloud infrastructures (65%), suggesting that future professionals need competencies that span both domains rather than being trained in isolated silos.

3.1.2 Training Delivery and Learning Format Preferences

A major theme emerging across the responses is the importance of flexible and modular learning pathways. Participants repeatedly indicate that MOOCs, online courses, and professional certifications can play an important role alongside formal degree programmes, especially for upskilling, re-skilling, and lifelong learning.

This preference is not only a matter of format, but also a response to structural barriers. The survey identifies limited time, budget constraints, and lack of internal expertise as key obstacles to workforce upskilling. These constraints are particularly visible among smaller organizations, which often require accessible and modular learning offers that can be integrated into existing work routines. However, similar constraints also affect individual lifelong learners, who may be balancing learning with professional and personal responsibilities.

These findings strongly support ACHIEVE's decision to release SSLMs online. In this context, online delivery is not simply a logistical choice, but a strategic enabler for inclusiveness and scalability. Modular online courses can support different learner profiles, including company employees, re-skilling professionals, and independent lifelong learners, by allowing progressive participation, selective topic uptake, and stackable learning trajectories.

3.1.3 Certifications and recognisable learning outcomes

The survey also highlights the importance of certified and recognizable competencies, while revealing a significant difference between Cloud and HPC. In the Cloud domain, respondents commonly view industry-recognized certifications as relevant for recruitment and career progression, and many organizations report that they encourage employees to pursue certification and, in several cases, provide financial support for training or certification activities.

In HPC, by contrast, responses suggest that standardized and widely recognized certification pathways are still limited. This asymmetry has important implications for ACHIEVE. It indicates that the project can create value in two complementary ways: first, by aligning selected Cloud-related modules with established competency expectations where appropriate; and second, by contributing to a more structured micro-credentialing landscape in HPC, where market demand exists but standardized recognition remains underdeveloped.

From the perspective of SSLM design, this means that learning outcomes should be clearly articulated and progressively stackable, so that ACHIEVE credentials are meaningful not only within academic pathways but also for professional progression and lifelong learning trajectories.

3.1.4 Implications for ACHIEVE SSLMs

Taken together, the survey findings validate ACHIEVE's strategy to integrate stackable online courses and certification-oriented modules alongside traditional master-level education. The evidence supports an educational architecture that is flexible, modular, and progressively certifiable, while remaining grounded in advanced and emerging topics relevant to HPC and Cloud.

In practical terms, this implies that ACHIEVE SSLMs should be designed to:

- address core and emerging HPC/Cloud topics identified by the survey, including architecture-level innovation themes (Q2);
- support hybrid competence profiles spanning HPC and Cloud ecosystems (Q2, Q3);
- strengthen applied understanding through scenario-based and problem-oriented online learning formats, rather than relying exclusively on direct operational platform training (Q3, Q4);
- remain accessible to multiple audiences, including company employees, re-skilling professionals, and lifelong learners (Q1, Q5, Q9);
- and provide clear, recognisable learning outcomes that can connect to existing certification ecosystems in Cloud and help structure new credential pathways in HPC (Q6–Q8).

Overall, the survey not only confirms the existence of a skills gap; it also provides a strong rationale for the specific design choices of ACHIEVE: online delivery, modularisation allowing learners to build towards full qualifications through the progressive recognition of smaller learning achievements, and a balanced focus on foundational understanding, innovation-oriented content, and transferable professional competence.

3.2 Patent Analysis

3.2.1 Topics Identified from the Patent Analysis

The results of patent analysis reveal a clear distinction between:

- *Foundational topics*, such as thermal and power management, interconnects, storage systems, and semiconductor packaging, which have been consistently present since the early 2000s;
- *Motor themes*, which represent the main drivers of current innovation, including the convergence of HPC with Cloud Computing, Big Data, and

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Artificial Intelligence, advanced software engineering techniques for HPC, and HPC system management;

- *Prominent niche topics*, such as quantum and classical cryptography, bioinformatics workflows, and other domain-specific HPC applications.

A key finding of the analysis is the strong application-driven nature of recent HPC innovation. A significant proportion of emerging topics are related to HPC applications, particularly in machine learning and artificial intelligence, as well as in scientific, industrial, and data-intensive domains. This highlights a shift from hardware-centric innovation towards usage-oriented, software- and application-level competencies.

Network and clustering analyses of topic co-occurrence further indicate increasing technological convergence, notably between HPC, Cloud infrastructures, AI/ML workflows, and advanced networking technologies. These convergence trends suggest growing demand for professionals capable of effectively using and integrating HPC resources, rather than designing low-level hardware components.

Overall, the patent-based analysis provides a forward-looking view of labour market needs, identifying both currently demanded and emerging skill areas. The findings were used as a primary input for the design of ACHIEVE self-standing modules, ensuring that the curriculum targets industry-relevant competencies aligned with ongoing technological innovation. Foundational, hardware-centric topics were excluded from curriculum design, as they primarily target HPC system manufacturers rather than users.

The analysis shows a strong shift towards application-driven HPC usage:

- Approximately 60% of emerging innovation topics relate to HPC applications,
- Machine Learning and AI dominate emerging applications, representing over half of post-2018 topics.

Key convergence patterns include:

- HPC with Cloud and virtualization technologies,
- Integration of AI/ML pipelines into traditional HPC workflows,
- Growing relevance of quantum computing and cryptography,
- Influence of 5G/6G networking on distributed and edge-enabled HPC.

Survey responses indicate that professionals primarily seek:

- Operational understanding of Cloud and HPC tools,
- Skills enabling efficient use of HPC as end-users, rather than system designers,
- Short, focused learning units with clear certification outcomes.

3.2.2 Results of Graph-Theoretic Grouping of Topics

A co-occurrence topic network was constructed using DTM results and clustered hierarchically with SNA software Pajek, revealing three distinct themes: basic, motor, and niche, given in Figure 4. Energized co-topic network with three clusters (from the article under review). Basic themes (green) cover physical components of HPC systems like connectors, thermal management sub-systems, and semiconductor packaging, while motor themes (yellow) focus on major applications, HPC convergence with Cloud/Big Data/AI, and management. Niche themes (red) include specialized topics like quantum cryptography, agricultural fluid dispensing systems, gesture recognition, etc.

applications. The full list of topics under these contents can be found in the files given in Appendices A and B.

Table 4. Contents on Cloud & HPC systems

ID	Content Name	# of Topics
1	Foundations & Core Parallelism	26
2	Scheduling, Orchestration & Resource Management	13
3	Virtualization & Cloud-Native HPC	16
4	Interconnects, RDMA & Datacenter Networking	45
5	Storage & Filesystems	35
6	Memory Systems, CXL & PIM	22
7	Processor Architecture & Micro-Optimizations	14
8	Checkpointing, Fault Tolerance & Reliability	13
9	Security, IAM & Trusted Platforms	23
10	Data Engineering, Streaming & Analytics	13
11	AI/ML on HPC & Accelerators	12
12	Programming Models, CUDA & Compilation	11
13	Accelerators, Dataflow & Systolic Arrays	10
14	Edge, IoT, Vehicular & Hybrid	10
15	Content Delivery, Multicast & Web-Scale Systems	14
16	Compression, ECC & Coding	10
17	Graphics, Geometry & Rendering	6
18	Datacenter Ops, Boot & Power	6
19	Ledgers, Security Analytics & Governance	7
20	Specialized/Advanced Systems Capstones	10
21	Edge Cases, Admin & Misc	7
22	Reconfigurable & Parallel Architectures	8
23	Remaining Specialized Topics	7

Table 5. Contents on HPC applications

ID	Content Name	# of Topics
1	Voice, Telephony & Contact-Center Systems	14
2	Supply Chain, Commerce & Logistics	5
3	Semiconductor & IC Design	5
4	EV, Energy & CleanTech	7
5	Advertisement, Search & Personalization	15
6	Content Controls and UX	38
7	Streaming, Gaming & Graphics Pipelines	31
8	Computer Vision, Imaging & XR	29
9	Autonomous Vehicles, Robotics & Sensing	25
10	Geoscience, Reservoirs & CFD	13
11	Built Environment & Industrial Control Systems	34
12	Bio, Pharma & ChemInformatics	24
13	Genomics, Healthcare & Medical Imaging	41
14	FinTech, Blockchain & Security	25
15	5G/6G, Wireless & Satellite	20
16	Web, Mobile, Documents & Edge	24
17	AI Dev, Code & QA	4
18	Home, IoT & Smart Spaces	7
19	Gesture Recognition & HCI	7
20	Physics, Simulation & Math	7
21	Social & Behavior Analytics	4
22	Data Mining, NLP & IR	4
23	Audio, Digital Signal Processing & Multimodal	9
24	Print/Display/Optics & Sensors	10
25	Quantum Computing	7

3.2.4 Prioritization of Contents

In Table 4 and Table 5 the contents are not listed in order of priority. To calculate the importance of each content, the weighted sum of the topic frequencies under each content was calculated using:

$$W_j = \left(\sum_{t \in M_j} 1.0 \cdot f_t \right) + \left(\sum_{t \in N_j} 0.6 \cdot f_t \right),$$

where:

- W The final Weighted Sum/Score for Module j.
- f The global frequency of topic t in the entire corpus. (BERTopic “Count” value per topic)
- M_j The set of Motor Topics that belong to Content j.
- N_j The set of Niche Topics that belong to Content j.

Different weights were tried based on the average degrees of motor and niche topic clusters. The lists remain unchanged, although there are slight differences in the order.

Table 6 and Table 7 show the top fifteen contents for both Cloud & HPC systems and HPC applications, respectively.

Table 6. Top-15 contents on Cloud & HPC systems

Priority Rank	Content Name	# of topics	Total frequency	Weighted Priority
1	Interconnects, RDMA & Datacenter Networking	45	1169	1014.2
2	Storage & Filesystems	35	996	991.6
3	Foundations & Core Parallelism	26	863	829
4	Memory Systems, CXL & PIM	22	885	779.4

5	AI/ML on HPC & Accelerators	12	651	651
6	Security, IAM & Trusted Platforms	23	633	480.2
7	Virtualization & Cloud-Native HPC	16	470	415.2
8	Compression, ECC & Coding	10	412	404
9	Accelerators, Dataflow & Systolic Arrays	10	398	392
10	Processor Architecture & Micro-Optimizations	14	429	385.4
11	Programming Models, CUDA & Compilation	11	369	328.6
12	Content Delivery, Multicast & Web-Scale Systems	14	383	323
13	Checkpointing, Fault Tolerance & Reliability	13	329	279.8
14	Scheduling, Orchestration & Resource Management	13	264	250
15	Data Engineering, Streaming & Analytics	13	255	223.4

Table 7. Top-15 contents on HPC applications

Priority Rank	Content Name	# of topics	Total frequency	Weighted Priority
1	Genomics, Healthcare & Medical Imaging	44	1236	919.6
2	Streaming, Gaming & Graphics Pipelines	31	846	796
3	Computer Vision, Imaging & XR	29	803	759.4
4	Content Controls and UX	38	796	706.8
5	Bio, Pharma & ChemInformatics	24	722	689.6
6	Autonomous Vehicles, Robotics & Sensing	25	781	637
7	Web, Mobile, Documents & Edge	24	601	592.2
8	Blockchain, FinTech & Security	25	722	556.8
9	Geoscience, Reservoirs & CFD	13	485	485
10	Voice, Telephony & Contact-Center Systems	14	478	478
11	Advertisement, Search & Personalization	15	363	358.2
12	Quantum Computing	7	345	337.4
13	5G/6G, Wireless & Satellite	20	498	332.4

14	Audio, Digital Signal Processing & Multimodal	9	295	281.8
15	Built Environment & Industrial Control Systems	17	386	252.4

3.2.5 Detailed Analyses of Emerging Topics After 2018

The emerging topics in the HPC-related patents after 2018 were also investigated. The analysis indicates a significant prevalence of HPC applications among emerging innovation topics, constituting 77 out of 129 identified themes (approximately 60%). Within these nascent HPC applications, Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) dominate, representing 41 of the 77 topics (about 53%).

Key Observations and Trends:

- **ML/AI Integration:** ML/AI is increasingly being integrated into traditional HPC domains, as evidenced by its application in fields such as seismic analysis, genomics, and computational biology (Topics 549, 671, and 814).
- **Technology Convergence:** Signals from different emerging topics suggest a technological convergence where ML/AI is reshaping not only HPC applications but also their fundamental system components and hardware. Consequently, ML/AI is both leveraging HPC infrastructure and simultaneously driving its transformation.
- **Critical Challenge:** From the analysis came out a critical hurdle for ML/AI in HPC: ensuring reproducibility at hyperscale levels during training.
- **Other Emerging Technologies:** Several other notable emerging technological clusters are poised to influence the HPC landscape, mirroring the transformative potential of ML/AI:
 - Virtualization and Cloud HPC
 - Quantum Computing and Cryptography
 - Advanced Telecommunications (i.e. the impact of 5G/6G telecommunications on the domain).
- **Conventional Development:** The remainder of the emerging topics consists of incremental advancements in the standard hardware and software components of HPC systems.

4 Curriculum Design for Self-Standing Modules

4.1 Proposed Self-Standing Learning Modules

Survey results and the prioritized target topics were shared with the consortium to inform the selection of self-standing learning modules. A consolidated list of SSLMs proposed by consortium partners was then collected and reviewed to assess the overall thematic coverage against the identified target contents. Given the breadth of the Cloud and Network Infrastructures and HPC domain and the diversity of learner profiles, a fully exhaustive coverage was neither feasible nor aligned with the intended positioning of the SSLMs, which aims to remain below doctoral/research-specialist level. Thanks to this coverage analysis, the consortium now has a clearer view of the areas that remain only partially covered or currently outside the scope of the proposed modules, and will assess in the next phase the possibility of integrating the current offering accordingly.

As a result, 23 SSLMs were identified to be developed under the ACHIEVE project. These SSLMs are listed in Table 8. A detailed syllabus of each course is provided in Appendix A.

Table 8: Self-Standing Learning Modules

Category	Course name	Course Level	Instructor	Institution
Business	Introduction to Information Systems	Intermediate	Erhan P. Eren	METU
	Cloud Computing: Technology and Business	Introductory	Erhan P. Eren	METU

Networking	Introduction to Computer Networking	Introductory	Altan Koçyiğit	METU
	Computing in Communication Networks	Intermediate	Fabrizio Granelli	UNITN
	Network Systems with Edge or Cloud Datacenters	Intermediate	Marco Chiesa	KTH
	Network Security	Introductory	Nazife Baykal	METU
Cloud infrastructure	Datacenter Computing Infrastructures: Design Principles and Technologies	Introductory	Gianluca Palermo, Danilo Ardagna	POLIMI
	Platforms and Systems for Cloud Computing	Advanced	Adrian Sterca, Sergiu Adrian Darabant, Virginia Niculescu, Horia Grebla	UBB
	Modern Cloud Architectures – Virtualization, Docker and Kubernetes	Intermediate	Guillaume Pierre	UR
	Performance Evaluation of Computing and Networked Systems	Intermediate	Viktoria Fodor	KTH
HPC	Parallel Programming in Rust	Intermediate	Dušan Gajić, DInu Dragan, Veljko Petrović, Branislav Ristić, Nikola Vukić	UNS FTN
	Effortless Parallelism	Introductory	Dušan Gajić, DInu Dragan, Veljko Petrović, Branislav Ristić, Nikola Vukić	UNS FTN
	Towards HPC: From Parallel Algorithmics (PRAM Model) to Shared Memory Programming (OpenMP) and Distributed Programming (MPI)	Intermediate	Cédric Tedeschi	UR
	Quantum Computing: A Software Engineering Perspective	Introductory	Elisabetta Di Nitto	POLIMI

	High-Performance Python: Profiling and Optimization for HPC	Introductory	Stefano Markidis	KTH
	Social Network Analysis	Intermediate	Banu Günel Kılıç	METU
	Devops Essentials	Intermediate	Kırçiçeği Korkmaz	METU
	Introduction to GPU Computing and CUDA Programming	Advanced	Alptekin Temizel	METU
Sustainability	Elements of Sustainable ICT - Introduction	Introductory	Jukka Manner	Aalto
	Elements of Sustainable ICT - Networking and Services	Introductory	Jukka Manner	Aalto
	Elements of Sustainable ICT - Green Software	Introductory	Jukka Manner	Aalto
	Elements of Sustainable ICT - Data Centers	Introductory	Jukka Manner	Aalto
	Elements of Sustainable ICT - Equipment (Electronics, manufacturing, repairing)	Introductory	Jukka Manner	Aalto

4.2 Course Coverage

To analyze the coverage of the SSLMs against the 30 prioritized contents (see Table 6 and Table 7), the syllabi of the SSLMs were aggregated. For each topic of each content, a semantic search was performed in the aggregated syllabi. If there is a match, the topic was marked to show that the topic shares significant technical keywords or themes with the course descriptions. Finally, the coverage was calculated by dividing the number of covered topics by the total number of topics of a content. This coverage analysis has been automated and made to cross-check with the quantitative analysis work. Table 9 and Table 10 show the coverage results.

Table 9. SSLM’s coverage for Top-15 contents on Cloud & HPC systems

Priority Rank	Content Name	# of topics	# of covered topics by SSLMs	Coverage (%)
1	Interconnects, RDMA & Datacenter Networking	45	25	55.6
2	Storage & Filesystems	35	23	65.7
3	Foundations & Core Parallelism	26	16	61.5
4	Memory Systems, CXL & PIM	22	13	59.1
5	AI/ML on HPC & Accelerators	12	5	41.7
6	Security, IAM & Trusted Platforms	23	9	39.1
7	Virtualization & Cloud-Native HPC	16	10	62.5
8	Compression, ECC & Coding	10	2	20.0
9	Accelerators, Dataflow & Systolic Arrays	10	7	70.0
10	Processor Architecture & Micro-Optimizations	14	4	28.6
11	Programming Models, CUDA & Compilation	11	6	54.5
12	Content Delivery, Multicast & Web-Scale Systems	14	7	50.0
13	Checkpointing, Fault Tolerance & Reliability	13	7	53.8
14	Scheduling, Orchestration & Resource Management	13	7	53.8
15	Data Engineering, Streaming & Analytics	13	8	61.5

Table 10. SSLM’s coverage for Top-15 contents on HPC applications

Priority Rank	Content Name	# of topics	# of covered topics by SSLMs	Coverage (%)
1	Genomics, Healthcare & Medical Imaging	41	2	4.9
2	Streaming, Gaming & Graphics Pipelines	31	6	19.4
3	Computer Vision, Imaging & XR	29	2	6.9
4	Content Controls and UX	38	8	21.1
5	Bio, Pharma & ChemInformatics	24	3	12.5
6	Autonomous Vehicles, Robotics & Sensing	25	3	12.0
7	Web, Mobile, Documents & Edge	24	12	50.0

8	Blockchain, FinTech & Security	25	7	28.0
9	Geoscience, Reservoirs & CFD	13	1	7.7
10	Voice, Telephony & Contact-Center Systems	14	3	21.4
11	Advertisement, Search & Personalization	15	3	20.0
12	Quantum Computing	7	5	71.4
13	5G/6G, Wireless & Satellite	20	10	50.0
14	Audio, Digital Signal Processing & Multimodal	9	0	0.0
15	Built Environment & Industrial Control Systems	17	2	11.8

On average, the SSLMs cover 53.8% of the top contents on Cloud and HPC Systems and 20.2% of the top contents on HPC applications. As expected, the match rate is lower for the latter, because these topics are highly specialized applications that have less direct overlap with the foundational HPC and Cloud Computing courses in the SSLM list. However, within SSLMs, after the coverage of fundamental topics, the patents can be provided as additional reading material for those who are interested in a specific application of cloud and HPC computing. A separate repository will be generated for this purpose. If further modules, or updates, will be developed within the project, the analysis will be updated.

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5 Certification Schemes Design

5.1 Certification Structure

The certification schemes developed within ACHIEVE are informed by existing European experiences in structuring modular and market-oriented certification frameworks in the field of digital skills. Such experiences (e.g. the CONCORDIA H2020 project) have highlighted the importance of flexibility, industry alignment, and progressive competence development. These principles have guided the design of the ACHIEVE certification approach, while the structure itself has been independently defined to address the specific needs of the HPC and Cloud ecosystem.

The ACHIEVE certification scheme adopts a modular and stackable structure that enables learners to progressively develop competencies and obtain formal recognition. The framework is organised around:

- *Learning Modules*
 - Short and focused modules addressing defined learning outcomes
 - Modules that can be followed independently or combined within structured learning paths
 - Content aligned with identified labour market needs and relevant professional roles in HPC and Cloud domains

- *Certification Pathways*
 - Certifications are awarded upon completion of a defined combination of mandatory and elective modules.
 - Support for different certification levels (e.g. foundational and advanced), allowing both horizontal skill broadening and vertical deepening of expertise.

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Assessment is integrated within each module and is designed to verify the acquisition of the intended learning outcomes. In the current implementation, evaluation is primarily based on structured online assessments. These tools are used to verify conceptual understanding, methodological knowledge, and familiarity with relevant tools and practices.

While practical and hands-on assessment components are recognised as valuable in principle, their implementation presents logistical and scalability challenges within the current project framework. Therefore, practical validation of competencies is, at this stage, mainly embedded within the learning activities themselves rather than through separate formal practical examinations.

Certifications and assessments are delivered through a digital learning and examination environment that ensures accessibility for professionals, scalability at European level, and traceability of results. The platform supports identity verification, exam integrity, and transparent issuance of certificates.

5.2 Delivery Platform and Assessment

Modules as well as the assessments will be hosted on the Icarus Platform. The self-standing learning modules and their associated assessments will be delivered through the **ICARUS Platform** (<https://eit.icarus.education/>), which serves as the reference digital learning environment for EIT Digital education activities.

The platform provides a centralized and scalable infrastructure for the hosting of learning materials, learner management, and assessment delivery. It supports modular and self-paced learning formats, enabling flexible access to course content and assessments for different target groups, including professionals, job seekers, and lifelong learners.

Assessment mechanisms are natively integrated into the platform and are aligned with the learning outcomes defined for each module and certification.

Assessments may include online theoretical examinations and applied evaluation activities, depending on the nature of the module.

The ICARUS Platform ensures traceability of learner participation and assessment results, supporting quality assurance and the issuance of certificates. The use of a common delivery and assessment platform enables consistent implementation across modules and facilitates scalability at European level.

5.3 Certificate Types

In this section, we introduce and present the certification paths developed within ACHIEVE, building upon the SSLMs previously described. Each certification (or learning) path is outlined in terms of its target audience, expected learning outcomes, and the structure of mandatory and elective modules required to obtain the certification.

Each certification path can be composed of a core set of mandatory modules, identified as the foundational building blocks for the respective topic area, complemented by a selection of elective modules. The elective components allow learners to tailor their pathway and determine the depth and level of the certification awarded.

5.3.1 ACHIEVE Certificate in HPC and Parallel Computing

Target Audience

- Professionals aiming to use HPC systems effectively
- Engineers and developers needing parallel programming skills
- Researchers working with compute-intensive applications

Learning Outcomes

Holders of this certificate will be able to:

- Understand HPC architectures and infrastructures
- Develop parallel applications
- Optimize performance using profiling and modeling
- Use GPUs and accelerators effectively
- Apply suitable parallelization strategies

Required Modules

Core Modules (Mandatory):

- High-Performance Python: Profiling and Optimization for HPC
- Towards HPC: From Parallel Algorithmics (PRAM Model) to Shared Memory Programming (OpenMP) and Distributed Programming (MPI)
- Introduction to GPU Computing and CUDA Programming

Specialization modules (choose at least one):

- Effortless Parallelism
- Parallel Programming in Rust
- Performance Evaluation of Computing and Networked Systems
- Datacenter Computing Infrastructures: Design Principles and Technologies
- Element of sustainable ICT.

Certificate Type

The BASIC certificate is awarded upon successful completion of all three core modules and at least one elective module. The ADVANCED certificate is awarded upon successful completion of all three core modules and at least four elective modules.

5.3.2 ACHIEVE Certificate in Cloud and Networked Computing Systems

Target Audience

- ICT professionals working with cloud and edge systems
- Engineers managing distributed and data center infrastructures
- Professionals supporting HPC–cloud integration

Learning Outcomes

Holders of this certificate will be able to:

- Design cloud and data center infrastructures
- Manage virtualized and containerized platforms
- Understand the different networking technologies and protocols
- Address basic security challenges in networked environments

Required Modules

Core modules (mandatory):

- Cloud Computing: Technology and Business
- Modern Cloud Architectures – Virtualization, Docker and Kubernetes
- Introduction of Computer Networking
- Computing in Communication Networks

Specialization modules (choose at least one):

- Datacenter Computing Infrastructures: Design Principles and Technologies
- Platforms and Systems for Cloud Computing
- Devops Essentials
- Network Systems with Edge or Cloud Datacenters

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- Performance Evaluation of Computing and Networked Systems
- Elements of Sustainable ICT - Data Centers
- Elements of Sustainable ICT – Networking and Services
- Network Security

Certificate Type

The BASIC certificate is awarded upon successful completion of all four core modules and at least one elective module. The ADVANCED certificate is awarded upon successful completion of all four core modules and at least five elective modules.

5.3.3 ACHIEVE Certificate in Sustainable and Green ICT

Target Audience

- ICT professionals concerned with sustainability and energy efficiency,
- Data center and infrastructure operators,
- Policy-aware engineers and technology managers.

Learning Outcomes

Holders of this certificate will be able to:

- Understand sustainability challenges in ICT systems,
- Apply green principles to software, networks, and data centers,
- Evaluate environmental impacts of AI and ICT manufacturing,
- Design more energy-efficient and responsible ICT solutions.

Required Modules

Core modules (mandatory):

- Elements of Sustainable ICT - Introduction
- Elements of Sustainable ICT - Green Software

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- Elements of Sustainable ICT - Data Centers
- Elements of Sustainable ICT - Networking and Services
- Elements of Sustainable ICT - Equipment (Electronics, manufacturing, repairing)

Certificate Type

The unique certificate is awarded upon successful completion of all five core modules.

5.3.4 ACHIEVE Certificate on Engineering Scalable Digital Infrastructures

Target Audience

- Professionals interested in the transition into cloud and infrastructure engineering
- Software developers expanding their expertise toward platform and infrastructure concerns
- Technical managers who need a system-level understanding of scalable digital infrastructures

Learning Outcomes

Holders of this certificate will be able to:

- Design scalable digital infrastructures
- Evaluate and select appropriate cloud service and deployment models
- Apply core networking principles and software-defined approaches
- Implement DevOps practices,
- Align digital infrastructure solutions with enterprise processes and digital transformation goals

Required Modules

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Core modules (mandatory):

- Cloud Computing: Technology and Business
- Datacenter Computing Infrastructures: Design Principles and Technologies
- Introduction to Information Systems
- Devops Essentials
- Introduction to Computer Networking

Certificate Type

The unique certificate is awarded upon successful completion of all five core modules.

5.4 Overview of the Achieve Learning Paths

The following table provides an overview of the courses offered by ACHIEVE and their mapping into the learning paths as CORE or as ELECVITE course.

Course name	HPC+ Parallel Programming	Cloud and Networked Computing Systems	Sustainable and Green ICT	Engineering Scalable Digital Infrastructures
Introduction to Information Systems				CORE
Cloud Computing: Technology and Business		CORE		CORE
Introduction to Computer Networking		CORE		CORE
Computing in Communication Networks		CORE		
Network Systems with Edge or Cloud Datacenters		ELECTIVE		
Network Security		ELECTIVE		
Datacenter Computing Infrastructures: Design Principles and Technologies		ELECTIVE		CORE
Platforms and Systems for Cloud Computing		ELECTIVE		
Modern Cloud Architectures – Virtualization, Docker and Kubernetes		CORE		
Performance Evaluation of Computing and Networked Systems	ELECTIVE	ELECTIVE		
Parallel Programming in Rust	ELECTIVE			
Effortless Parallelism	ELECTIVE			
Towards HPC: From Parallel Algorithmics (PRAM Model) to Shared Memory Programming (OpenMP) and Distributed Programming (MPI)	CORE			
Quantum Computing: A Software Engineering Perspective	ELECTIVE			
High-Performance Python: Profiling and Optimization for HPC	CORE			
Social Network Analysis	ELECTIVE			
Devops Essentials		ELECTIVE		CORE
Introduction to GPU Computing and CUDA Programming	CORE			
Elements of Sustainable ICT - Introduction			CORE	
Elements of Sustainable ICT - Networking and Services		ELECTIVE	CORE	
Elements of Sustainable ICT - Green Software	ELECTIVE		CORE	
Elements of Sustainable ICT - Data Centers		ELECTIVE	CORE	
Elements of Sustainable ICT - Equipment			CORE	

6 Conclusions and Next Steps

Task 3.1 has successfully delivered a comprehensive market analysis to support the design of ACHIEVE’s self-standing learning modules (SSLMs) and related learning paths. The work combined complementary methods in order to capture both demand-side skills needs and technology-side innovation trends. In particular, the analysis included a qualitative assessment based on survey evidence (with a focus on skills needs, training preferences, barriers to upskilling, and the role of certifications in HPC and Cloud) and, for the HPC domain, a more detailed topic-level investigation informed by patent analysis. This dual approach made it possible to connect market expectations, emerging technological directions, and educational planning within a single evidence-based framework.

Building on these findings, the document does not only report the analysis results, but also translates them into concrete curriculum design choices. It presents the set of SSLMs planned within ACHIEVE, the rationale for their thematic coverage, and the way these modules are organized into coherent learning paths. It also outlines how the learning paths are associated with progressive certification opportunities, with the aim of supporting different learner profiles, including up-skilling and re-skilling participants, as well as more general lifelong learning trajectories. In this sense, the document provides both the analytical basis and the initial curricular architecture for ACHIEVE’s training offer.

Overall, Task 3.1 establishes a robust foundation for the next implementation phases of the project by ensuring that module development and certification planning are grounded in documented market needs, observed skills gaps, and emerging innovation areas. The next steps will build on this foundation through the development and integration of the SSLMs, the refinement of learning pathways, and the operationalization of the corresponding certification schemes.

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APPENDIX A: Course Syllabi

This appendix presents the syllabi of the Self-Standing Learning Modules (SSLMs) to be developed within the ACHIEVE project. Each module is described through a structured template designed to provide a clear and comparable overview of its content and pedagogical approach. In particular, each syllabus includes a Catalog Description (brief module description), prerequisites, Course Objectives, Learning Outcomes, Course Outline, Materials, and a short bio of the instructors. The purpose of this appendix is to provide a transparent overview of the planned training offer, highlighting their contribution to competence development in the HPC and Cloud domains.

In order to improve transparency, comparability, and the structuring of stackable learning paths, the ACHIEVE self-standing learning modules (SSLMs) are being positioned against the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) through an indicative, learning-outcomes-based approach. The alignment is derived from each syllabus (in particular, prerequisites, course objectives, learning outcomes, and expected learner autonomy), and refers to the EQF dimensions of knowledge, skills, and responsibility/autonomy. Given the diversity of the SSLM portfolio, the current set of modules spans a range from foundational/intermediate content to advanced technical topics, with most modules expected to fall within EQF 6, and selected advanced modules supporting progression towards EQF 7 when embedded in higher-level pathways and assessed through tasks requiring stronger analytical judgment, integration, and autonomy. This positioning is indicative and intended to support curriculum design, pathway articulation, and future micro-credential schemes; it does not imply formal qualification recognition.

Deliverable D3.1: ACHIEVE Self-
Standing Modules: Market analysis and
curriculum design

Project: ACHIEVE (101190015)

Cloud Computing: Technology and Business

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course provides an overview of technical and business issues in cloud computing and highlights the trends in this rapidly evolving information technology area. The course content covers cloud computing fundamentals; benefits and challenges associated with cloud computing; building blocks and models; reference architecture; cloud services; current cloud computing platforms; use cases and applications; economics issues related to cloud computing; business implications; recent technological developments. Current topics and application areas in cloud computing are explored from various aspects highlighting technical and business issues.

PREREQUISITES

- Basic understanding of computing and business concepts.

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to

- Understand and explain the key concepts related to cloud computing
- Understand the different models for deploying cloud computing
- Evaluate the benefits and challenges associated with cloud computing
- Explore various use cases of cloud computing

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

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- Understood the basic building blocks of cloud computing
- Explored the different deployment and service models of cloud computing
- Seen various applications of cloud computing
- Identified economics issues related to cloud computing

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

History of Cloud Computing

Cloud Computing Fundamentals

Service Models

- Software as a Service, Infrastructure as a Service, Platform as a Service

Deployment Models

- Private, Public, Community, Hybrid Cloud

Benefits of Cloud Computing

Challenges and Obstacles

A Reference Architecture for Cloud Computing

Enabler Technologies for Cloud Computing

Cloud Computing Platforms

Economics of Cloud Computing

Use Cases and Applications

Additional topics (Edge Computing, Serverless, Cloud-native, FinOps)

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- Erl, T., and Monroy, E. (2023). Cloud Computing: Concepts, Technology, Security, and Architecture (The Pearson Digital Enterprise Series from Thomas Erl) Second Edition
- Manvi, S., and Shyam, G. (2021) Cloud Computing, Concepts and Technologies, CRC Press
- Liu, F. , Tong, J. , Mao, J. , Bohn, R. , Messina, J. , Badger, M. and Leaf, D. (2011), NIST Cloud Computing Reference Architecture, Special Publication (NIST SP), National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, MD, [online], <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.500-292>, https://tsapps.nist.gov/publication/get_pdf.cfm?pub_id=909505 (Accessed January 19, 2026)
- Armbrust, M., Fox, A., Griffith, R., Joseph, A. D., Katz, R., Konwinski, A., ... & Zaharia, M. (2010). A view of cloud computing. Communications of the ACM, 53(4), 50-58.

COURSE CONDUCT

Each chapter provides explanations of the fundamental concepts and their practical implications.

After each chapter, a short multiple-choice quiz will be used to evaluate students' understanding of the key concepts and reinforce their learning.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNEMENT

EQF 5-6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address foundational-to-intermediate knowledge of cloud computing concepts, deployment/service models, and business implications, while supporting the ability to compare cloud approaches and evaluate benefits, challenges, and use cases in organizational contexts.

INSTRUCTOR

Prof. P. Erhan Eren is a faculty member of the Information Systems Department and also the chair of Data Informatics Department at Informatics Institute, METU. He received his B.S. degree in Electrical and Electronics Engineering at Bilkent University. He was a teaching and research assistant during his graduate studies at University of Rochester, where he received his M.S. and Ph.D. degrees. During his Ph.D. studies, he also served as a technical consultant for image/video processing projects at Eastman Kodak Research Labs, Rochester, NY. He was a Senior Staff Research Engineer at Motorola Corporate Research Labs, Schaumburg, IL, and worked there for seven years. His research interests and graduate-level teaching subjects include data-driven organizations, big data, cloud computing, artificial intelligence applications, digital transformation, and management information systems.

Computing in Communication Networks

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

The course introduces the concepts of Software Defined Networking and Network Function Virtualization as the two building blocks for the integration of computing within the communication infrastructure. The course is based on theoretical and hands-on lectures. A dedicated Virtual Machine will be available to the students for hands-on experiments and other practical coursework.

PREREQUISITES

- Understanding of fundamental networking concepts (TCP/IP stack, networking 101)
- Basic proficiency in python programming language (preferably in C, C++ or Python)
- Basic proficiency in Linux

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to

- Understand and explain the key concepts related to Software Defined Networking and Network Function Virtualization
- Develop solutions exploiting the concept of computing in communication networks (edge computing, network slicing, 5G virtualization)
- Design and implement SDN and NFV solutions

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COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- the capability to apply the basic principles and concepts of network slicing and network function virtualization
- the capability to implement and deploy slicing and virtualization in emulated and real scenarios
- the capability to build testbeds and experiments on Software Defined Networking and Network Function Virtualization
- the capability to design innovative solutions for next-generation networking

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

PART 1 INTRODUCTION: FUTURE COMMUNICATION NETWORKS AND SYSTEMS

- On the Need of Computing in Future Communication Networks
- Standardization Activities for Future Communication Networks
- Introduction to the hands-on environment:
 - o Mininet: An Instant Virtual Network on Your Computer
 - o Docker: Containerize Your Network Function
 - o ComNetsEmu: The Lightweight Emulator developed for the course
 - o Other useful networking tools

PART 2 KEY THEORETICAL CONCEPTS

- Network Slicing
- Mobile Edge Cloud
- Content Distribution

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PART 3 ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES

- Software-Defined Networking (with hands-on lab on OpenFlow and RYU controller)
- Network Function Virtualization (with hands-on lab on docker)

PART 4 DEPLOYING IN-NETWORK INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

- Implementing network slicing in single tenant and multi-tenant scenarios
- Service migration in MEC scenarios
- Deploying a 5G private network using open source implementations

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- Frank H.P. Fitzek, F. Granelli, P. Seeling, “Computing in Communication Networks – From Theory to Practice,” Academic Press.

COURSE CONDUCT

After each chapter, a short multiple-choice quiz will be used to evaluate students’ understanding of the key concepts and reinforce their learning.

Each chapter begins with an explanation of the underlying theoretical concepts and progresses to hands-on practical exercises.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNEMENT

EQF 6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address advanced knowledge of computing-enabled communication networks and support learners in analyzing architectural options, system interactions, and performance-related design considerations in networked environments.

INSTRUCTOR

Prof. Fabrizio Granelli fabrizio.granelli@unitn.it

Fabrizio Granelli is Full Professor at the University of Trento (Italy) and visiting professor at the State University of Campinas (Brasil) and the University of Tokyo (Japan). He has 26 years of experience in ComSoc, as Distinguished Lecturer (2012-15 and 2021-24), Director for Online Content (2016-17), Director for Educational Services (2018-19) and Director for Conference Development (2022-23). Prof. Granelli was General or TPC Chair of several prestigious IEEE conferences, including IEEE Globecom, IEEE NFV-SDN, IEEE CAMAD, and chaired several ICC/Globecom symposia. He founded the ComSoc Summer Schools, the Aerial Communication ETI, the IEEE P1954 Standard WG, and IEEE ICMLC (International Conference on Machine Learning for Communications) and IEEE MECOM (Middle East Conference on Communications and Networking). He was Associate EiC of IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials (2017-2022), and currently Senior Editor of IEEE Transactions on Green Communications and Networking. He is author of 300+ papers on communications and networking topics.

Datacenter Computing Infrastructures: Design Principles and Technologies

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

Modern large-scale datacenters require the seamless integration of different components - applications, computation nodes, storage devices, and networks - into one computing infrastructure. The course covers the basics of current datacenter architectures, ranging from the analysis of the single components to the global infrastructure. The focus is on the foundations required to understand the design of modern computing infrastructures that are scalable, available, secure, and flexible at the same time.

PREREQUISITES

- Basic Knowledge of Computer Systems
- Introductory understanding of Cloud Computing and HPC

COURSE OBJECTIVES

The course equips learners with the conceptual and technical foundations required to understand, evaluate, and contribute to the design of scalable, efficient, and future-ready data center infrastructures.

The objective of this course is to provide the students with a structured understanding of how modern data center computing infrastructures are conceived and designed to support contemporary digital workloads. The course aims to bridge the gap between facility-level infrastructure and computing architecture, allowing students to understand how design choices in power, cooling, compute, storage, and networking influence performance, scalability, and sustainability. By the end of the course, learners will have

developed the conceptual foundation necessary to critically engage with data center design decisions, with particular relevance to cloud, AI, and HPC environments.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to

- Understand the key concepts related to modern computing infrastructures;
- Describe the fundamental components of datacenter computing infrastructures, including facility systems, compute, storage, and networking layers;
- Explain the design principles behind power distribution, cooling, and energy efficiency in modern data centers
- Analyze the relationship between application workloads (cloud, AI, HPC) and datacenter architectural choices.
- Compare different design options for compute, storage, and network architectures in terms of scalability, performance, and sustainability
- Evaluate datacenter design solutions against technical, efficiency, and future-readiness criteria.
- Contribute to informed discussions on the design of datacenter infrastructures within multidisciplinary technical teams.
- Understand and autonomously learn the impact of novel technologies and trends within computing infrastructures

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COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

- Introduction to Datacenter Computing Infrastructures
- Datacenter Architectural Overview
- Hardware Building Blocks
- Building, Power, and Cooling
- Energy and Power Efficiency
- Datacenter Costs and Failure

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- *Luiz André Barroso and Urs Hölzle, The Datacenter as a Computer: An Introduction to the Design of Warehouse-Scale Machines.*
- *Further Material will be provided by the instructors*

COURSE CONDUCT

Each module starts with an explanation of the underlying theoretical concepts and continues with readings suggested by the instructor. After each module, a short multiple-choice quiz will be used to evaluate students' understanding of the key concepts and reinforce their learning.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address advanced knowledge of datacenter computing infrastructures and the ability to analyze, compare, and evaluate infrastructure design choices, while also supporting responsibility/autonomy through informed technical discussion and independent updating of knowledge.

INSTRUCTOR

Gianluca Palermo is Full Professor at Politecnico di Milano, Department of Electronics, Information and Bioengineering, with expertise in digital design, high-performance computing and advanced computing infrastructures. His research focuses on system-level and low-power design, application autotuning, and large-scale HPC platforms, with particular emphasis on computational methods for drug discovery, including molecular docking at scale. Since 2020, he has been teaching the Computing Infrastructure course at Politecnico di Milano, a mandatory course for all students enrolled in the Computer Science and Engineering degree as well as in the HPC programme, where he covers architectures, performance optimization, and the design and management of modern Data Center infrastructures.

DevOps Essentials

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course provides the essential knowledge on the DevOps concepts and skills. Starting with an introduction to what DevOps is and the DevOps culture, the course covers the necessary components of the DevOps lifecycle, build automation, continuous integration and continuous delivery, infrastructure as code, configuration management, orchestration and monitoring. The course covers the microservices architecture and the DevOps pipeline. The relationship between cloud computing and DevOps is described with hands-on examples of different cloud platforms.

PREREQUISITES

Prior experience in software development

COURSE OBJECTIVES

Upon successful completion of this course, students will be able to

- Explain the fundamental concepts, principles, and culture of DevOps.
- Describe the stages, processes, and tools involved in the DevOps lifecycle.
- Understand the role of automation, continuous integration, and continuous delivery in software development.
- Explain how infrastructure as code, configuration management, orchestration, and monitoring support DevOps practices.
- Understand the relationship between DevOps and cloud computing platforms.
- Apply DevOps concepts and tools in software development projects.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

Upon successful completion of this course, students will

- Have the essential knowledge on the basic DevOps concepts and DevOps culture.
- Know the necessary components of the DevOps lifecycle.
- Be able to establish and manage the DevOps lifecycle in software organizations.
- Be able to practice build automation, continuous integration/delivery and configuration management in software projects
- Be able to use DevOps related technologies in their projects.

COURSE OUTLINE

- Introduction to DevOps and the DevOps Culture
- Build Automation and Continuous Integration
- Continuous Delivery and Continuous Deployment
- Infrastructure as Code
- Configuration Management
- Orchestration and Monitoring
- The DevOps Pipeline
- Microservices and the Serverless Architecture
- DevOps and the Cloud
- DevOps on Google Cloud Platform
- DevOps on Microsoft Azure
- DevOps on Amazon Web Services

TEXTBOOKS AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- DevOps: A Comprehensive Beginners Guide to Learn DevOps Step By Step, Ethan Thorpe, AKC publishing LLC, 2019.
- The DevOps Handbook: How to Create World-Class Agility, Reliability and Security in Technology Organizations, 2nd ed., IT Revolution Press, 2021.
- Effective DevOps: Building a Culture of Collaboration, Affinity and Tooling at Scale, Jennifer Davis & Ryn Daniels O'Reilly Media, 2016
- Liming Zhu, Len Bass, George Champlin-Scharff, DevOps and Its Practices, IEEE Software, Volume 33, Issue 3, 32-34. 39, 2016.
- M. Virmani, "Understanding DevOps & Bridging the Gap from Continuous Integration to Continuous Delivery", Proc. 5th Int'l Conf. Innovative Computing Technology, pp. 78-82, 2015.
- D. Spinellis, "Don't Install Software by Hand", IEEE Software, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 86-87, 2012.
- J. Hernantes, G. Gallardo, N. Serrano, "IT Infrastructure-Monitoring Tools", IEEE Software, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 88-93, 2015.
- Nicolás Paez, "Versioning Strategy for DevOps Implementations", Ciencias de la Informática y Desarrollos de Investigación (CACIDI) 2018 Congreso Argentino de, pp. 1-6, 2018.

COURSE CONDUCT

- Lectures covering theoretical foundations
- Practical demonstrations and case studies

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNEMENT

EQF 6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address applied knowledge of DevOps principles, automation practices, and lifecycle integration, and support learners in analyzing workflows, applying

tools and practices in structured settings, and evaluating operational trade-offs across development and deployment pipelines.

INSTRUCTOR

Dr. Kırçiçeği Korkmaz is an academic and software engineering professional with interdisciplinary expertise in computer engineering, bioinformatics, and large-scale software systems. She holds a Ph.D. in Computer Engineering from Middle East Technical University (METU), where her research focused on data mining and analysis of microarray gene expression data, with an emphasis on identifying biologically meaningful gene sets. Dr. Korkmaz is currently a part-time lecturer at METU's Graduate School of Informatics, contributing to graduate-level education in information systems. Alongside her academic work, she has extensive industry experience as a software engineer and technical lead, specializing in Java-based enterprise systems, cloud-native architectures, and DevOps practices. Her work bridges research and practice, combining data-driven methodologies with real-world software development and system design.

Effortless Parallelism

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course is intended to give data scientists Rust superpowers! The target audience are people whose day to day involves using a lot of Python to process and analyze information in data science and AI applications. When the built-in tools written in high-performance languages do not fit the needs of the computation at hand, and pure Python is simply not fast enough it becomes necessary to reach for something else. This course offers a simple tech stack that provides the simplest and most effective way to write powerful parallelized and incredibly high-performance code that integrates with your existing Python solution. The course covers the fundamentals of Rust, tailored to the needs of the course, tools and techniques that can integrate Rust with Python, and effortless high-performance parallelization with Rayon.

PREREQUISITES

- Understanding of fundamental programming concepts
- Proficiency in Python

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to

- Develop highly efficient Rust 'kernels' that they can integrate into existing Python projects that provide extreme speed where needed and get out of the way otherwise.
- Explain the basics of work-stealing parallelism.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Written fast Rust code that can be used in Python.
- Parallelised iterator-centric Rust dataflows using Rayon.

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

- Enough Rust to be Dangerous:
 - Setting up a Rust environment
 - Cargo and dependency management
 - Variables, loops, conditionals, and types in Rust.
 - The power of iterators in Rust
 - Functions, structs, traits, and enums
 - Error handling in Rust
- Talking to Python
 - maturin for scaffolding projects
 - PyO3 for exposing Rust functionality to python
 - Annotating functions, classes, and methods
 - Library initialization code
 - Interoperability with numpy
 - Disabling GIL with `allow_threads` for maximum performance

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- Effortless parallelism
 - Replacing loops with iterators
 - List comprehension and iterators
 - Rayon to turn iterator-based constructs into highly parallel code

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- Klabnik, Steve, and Carol Nichols. The Rust programming language. No Starch Press, 2023. (and modern online iterations).
- Rust by Example, <https://doc.rust-lang.org/rust-by-example/>
- Rustlings, <https://rustlings.rust-lang.org/>
- Rayon documentations via <https://docs.rs/rayon/latest/rayon/>

COURSE CONDUCT

At the end of each chapter of the course, students will be given exercise problems that they will work to independently solve before they are evaluated at the start of the next chapter. The results of these evaluations will track each student's progress, and this start-of-chapter session will be used to make sure that everyone understands the solution to these exercises before progressing.

Each chapter will be preceded by assigned reading from the reference documentation. Then, at the start of the class period an overview of this material will be presented. This overview's key purpose is to identify weaknesses in the student's understanding of the material and to remedy these weaknesses. This is followed by a series of exercises that are partially done by the student themselves, and partially demonstrated by the instructor.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

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EQF 6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address applied and conceptual knowledge of parallel programming abstractions and support learners in identifying opportunities for parallel execution, selecting suitable parallelization strategies, and evaluating performance implications in modern computing workloads.

INSTRUCTOR

Prof. Veljko Petrović

Prof. Dušan Gajić

Prof. Dinu Dragan

Nikola Vukić

Branislav Ristić

Elements of Sustainable ICT – ICT Equipment

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

The ICT sector is praised for its tremendous impact on our society. ICT enhances the productivity and processes of all industries. Consumers and companies have gained valuable new digital services that help us in our daily lives.

Yet, at the same time, the ICT sector has a considerable footprint from the energy use, manufacturing of devices and recycling (E-Waste). The goal of this course is to present this footprint, what the impact is on our environment and society, and how it could be lowered and thereby reduce our carbon emissions and impact on global warming.

This course focuses on the manufacturing and repairing of ICT equipment, and the environmental impact associated to the ICT hardware.

PREREQUISITES

- Understanding of ICT in general, what constitutes our daily digital life
- Understanding energy production and energy usage on a general level
- Ability to read technical and scientific publications

COURSE OBJECTIVES

The course equips learners with the conceptual and technical foundations required to understand, evaluate, and contribute to the design of more sustainable and energy-efficient digital services.

The objective of this course is to provide the students with a structured understanding of how our digital infrastructure uses energy and material

resources and thereby creates a major negative footprint on our society and environment. The course aims to raise awareness of the footprint of ICT and what is being done and what more can be done to support our goal towards a greener future. By the end of the course, learners will have an understanding of the wide impact of ICT resource usage, and how digital services could be built to be more resource efficient.

The objective of this course is to give the students a holistic understanding of the environmental impact of ICT hardware (smart phones, laptops, servers, etc.) during their lifecycle.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Understand the impact of the manufacturing process of electronics
- Understand the different stakeholders and their motives
- Understand how reparability has evolved and the future outlook in this area
- Identify potential places for reducing the environmental impact of ICT devices
- Differences between device types and device structure
- Regulation impacting the industry

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus
Introduction
What's in an ICT device?
Emissions from manufacturing

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How to make manufacturing more sustainable?

Repairability of ICT equipment: the big picture

How has repairability evolved?

Measuring repairability

Future directions and EU goals

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- All material is composed of public technical reports, scientific publications and similar documents, also potentially some online video material

COURSE CONDUCT

The course has an introductory lecture taking the student to the topic and explaining the key concepts. The self-study is based on scientific publications, industry reports and similar documents, and videos in some cases, that take the student deeper into the topic. This self-study is evaluated through multiple-choice quizzes. The grading is based on the quizzes.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 5-6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address structured knowledge of ICT equipment lifecycle impacts and sustainability considerations, while supporting learners in identifying environmental implications of equipment choices and discussing improvement options in relation to digital infrastructure use.

INSTRUCTOR

Professor, PhD., Jukka Manner, Aalto University, Department of Information and Communication Engineering (DICE)

Jukka Manner received his MSc. (1999) and PhD. (2004) degrees in computer science from the University of Helsinki. He is a full professor (tenured) of networking technology at Aalto University, Department of Communications and Networking (Comnet). His research and teaching focuses on networking, software and distributed systems, with a strong focus on wireless and mobile networks, transport protocols, energy efficient ICT and cyber security. The past years his primary research focus has been on the sustainability of ICT at large. He has contributed to standardization of Internet technologies in the IETF since 1999, and was the co-chair of the NSIS working group. He has been principal investigator and project manager for over 15 national and international research projects. He has authored over 200 publications, including eleven IETF RFCs.

Elements of Sustainable ICT - Data centres

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

The ICT sector is praised for its tremendous impact on our society. ICT enhances the productivity and processes of all industries. Consumers and companies have gained valuable new digital services that help us in our daily lives. Yet, at the same time, the ICT sector has a considerable footprint from the energy use, manufacturing of devices and recycling (E-Waste). The goal of this course is to present this footprint, what the impact is on our environment and society, and how it could be lowered and thereby reduce our carbon emissions and impact on global warming.

This module discusses data centres, their environmental impact, energy use, and energy flows.

PREREQUISITES

- Understanding of ICT in general, what constitutes our daily digital life
- Understanding energy production and energy usage on a general level
- Ability to read technical and scientific publications

COURSE OBJECTIVES

The course equips learners with the conceptual and technical foundations required to understand, evaluate, and contribute to the design of more sustainable and energy-efficient digital services.

The objective of this course is to provide the students with a structured understanding of how our digital infrastructure uses energy and material resources and thereby creates a major negative footprint on our society and

environment. The course aims to raise awareness of the footprint of ICT and what is being done and what more can be done to support our goal towards a greener future. By the end of the course, learners will have an understanding of the wide impact of ICT resource usage, and how digital services could be built to be more resource efficient.

This course gives the student a holistic understanding of data centres and their energy and sustainability impacts.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Understand what creates a data centre
- Understand the overall energy consumption of data centres and energy flows
- Understand the equipment and evolution of data centres

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus
Introduction
Core Concepts of a Data Center
Energy Efficiency and Sustainability Metrics for DCs
Waste Heat Utilization in DC
Energy Efficiency Optimization in DCs
Future

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- All material is composed of public technical reports, scientific publications and similar documents, also potentially some online video material

COURSE CONDUCT

The course has an introductory lecture taking the student to the topic and explaining the key concepts. The self-study is based on scientific publications, industry reports and similar documents, and videos in some cases, that take the student deeper into the topic. This self-study is evaluated through multiple-choice quizzes. The grading is based on the quizzes.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address applied knowledge of data centre components, energy flows, and sustainability metrics, and support learners in analyzing efficiency-related design issues and discussing optimization directions for more sustainable infrastructures.

INSTRUCTOR

Professor, PhD., Jukka Manner, Aalto University, Department of Information and Communication Engineering (DICE)

Jukka Manner received his MSc. (1999) and PhD. (2004) degrees in computer science from the University of Helsinki. He is a full professor (tenured) of networking technology at Aalto University, Department of Communications and Networking (Comnet). His research and teaching focuses on networking, software and distributed systems, with a strong focus on wireless and mobile networks, transport protocols, energy efficient ICT and cyber security. The past years his primary research focus has been on the sustainability of ICT at large. He has contributed to standardization of Internet technologies in the IETF

since 1999, and was the co-chair of the NSIS working group. He has been principal investigator and project manager for over 15 national and international research projects. He has authored over 200 publications, including eleven IETF RFCs.

Elements of Sustainable ICT - Introduction

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

The ICT sector is praised for its tremendous impact on our society. ICT enhances the productivity and processes of all industries. Consumers and companies have gained valuable new digital services that help us in our daily lives.

Yet, at the same time, the ICT sector has a considerable footprint from the energy use, manufacturing of devices and recycling (E-Waste). The goal of this course is to present this footprint, what the impact is on our environment and society, and how it could be lowered and thereby reduce our carbon emissions and impact on global warming.

PREREQUISITES

- Understanding of ICT in general, what constitutes our daily digital life
- Understanding energy production and energy usage on a general level
- Ability to read technical and scientific publications

COURSE OBJECTIVES

The course equips learners with the conceptual and technical foundations required to understand, evaluate, and contribute to the design of more sustainable and energy-efficient digital services.

The objective of this course is to provide the students with a structured understanding of how our digital infrastructure uses energy and material resources and thereby creates a major negative footprint on our society and

environment. The course aims to raise awareness of the footprint of ICT and what is being done and what more can be done to support our goal towards a greener future. By the end of the course, learners will have an understanding of the wide impact of ICT resource usage, and how digital services could be built to be more resource efficient.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Understand what creates our whole ICT environment
- Understand the overall ICT energy consumption
- Understand the manufacturing of ICT equipment, and the materials and recycling involved
- Understand software engineering from a sustainability angle
- Evaluate different digital services and their environmental impact
- Assess and measure digital services and e.g. their data usage
- Identify potential places for optimising the sustainability of a digital service

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus
Introduction
Evolution of ICT hardware and performance
Energy use of the ICT sector
Data centers and the recent AI boom
Manufacturing, recycling and repairing ICT hardware
Software Engineering

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- All material is composed of public technical reports, scientific publications and similar documents, also potentially some online video material

COURSE CONDUCT

The course has an introductory lecture taking the student to the topic and explaining the key concepts. The self-study is based on scientific publications, industry reports and similar documents, and videos in some cases, that take the student deeper into the topic. This self-study is evaluated through multiple-choice quizzes. The grading is based on the quizzes.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 5-6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address broad conceptual knowledge of ICT sustainability, environmental footprint, and resource use across digital infrastructures and services, while supporting learners in evaluating impacts and identifying opportunities for sustainability improvements.

INSTRUCTOR

Professor, PhD., Jukka Manner, Aalto University, Department of Information and Communication Engineering (DICE)

Jukka Manner received his MSc. (1999) and PhD. (2004) degrees in computer science from the University of Helsinki. He is a full professor (tenured) of networking technology at Aalto University, Department of Communications and Networking (Comnet). His research and teaching focuses on networking, software and distributed systems, with a strong focus on wireless and mobile

networks, transport protocols, energy efficient ICT and cyber security. The past years his primary research focus has been on the sustainability of ICT at large. He has contributed to standardization of Internet technologies in the IETF since 1999, and was the co-chair of the NSIS working group. He has been principal investigator and project manager for over 15 national and international research projects. He has authored over 200 publications, including eleven IETF RFCs.

Elements of Sustainable ICT - Networking and services

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

The ICT sector is praised for its tremendous impact on our society. ICT enhances the productivity and processes of all industries. Consumers and companies have gained valuable new digital services that help us in our daily lives. Yet, at the same time, the ICT sector has a considerable footprint from the energy use, manufacturing of devices and recycling (E-Waste). The goal of this course is to present this footprint, what the impact is on our environment and society, and how it could be lowered and thereby reduce our carbon emissions and impact on global warming.

This course focuses on the energy use of networking technologies and how Internet service design impacts resource usage.

PREREQUISITES

- Understanding of ICT in general, what constitutes our daily digital life
- Understanding energy production and energy usage on a general level
- Ability to read technical and scientific publications

COURSE OBJECTIVES

The course equips learners with the conceptual and technical foundations required to understand, evaluate, and contribute to the design of more sustainable and energy-efficient digital services.

The objective of this course is to provide the students with a structured understanding of how our digital infrastructure uses energy and material resources and thereby creates a major negative footprint on our society and

environment. The course aims to raise awareness of the footprint of ICT and what is being done and what more can be done to support our goal towards a greener future. By the end of the course, learners will have an understanding of the wide impact of ICT resource usage, and how digital services could be built to be more resource efficient.

This course seeks to give students a holistic understanding of the sustainability and environmental impact of networking technologies and digital services.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Understand the evolution of networking technology
- Understand the energy consumption of networking, fixed and wireless
- Understand how different digital services consume resources
- Understand design choices in digital services for the Internet
- Identify potential places for optimising a web-based digital service

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus
Introduction
Evolution of networking
Evolution of Internet content
Wireless communications
Digital services
Conclusions

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- All material is composed of public technical reports, scientific publications and similar documents, also potentially some online video material

COURSE CONDUCT

The course has an introductory lecture taking the student to the topic and explaining the key concepts. The self-study is based on scientific publications, industry reports and similar documents, and videos in some cases, that take the student deeper into the topic. This self-study is evaluated through multiple-choice quizzes. The grading is based on the quizzes.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address knowledge of networking evolution, resource consumption, and service-level sustainability issues, and support learners in identifying optimization opportunities and discussing design choices for more sustainable digital services.

INSTRUCTOR

Professor, PhD., Jukka Manner, Aalto University, Department of Information and Communication Engineering (DICE)

Jukka Manner received his MSc. (1999) and PhD. (2004) degrees in computer science from the University of Helsinki. He is a full professor (tenured) of networking technology at Aalto University, Department of Communications and Networking (Comnet). His research and teaching focuses on networking, software and distributed systems, with a strong focus on wireless and mobile networks, transport protocols, energy efficient ICT and cyber security. The past

years his primary research focus has been on the sustainability of ICT at large. He has contributed to standardization of Internet technologies in the IETF since 1999, and was the co-chair of the NSIS working group. He has been principal investigator and project manager for over 15 national and international research projects. He has authored over 200 publications, including eleven IETF RFCs.

Elements of Sustainable ICT – Green Software

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

The ICT sector is praised for its tremendous impact on our society. ICT enhances the productivity and processes of all industries. Consumers and companies have gained valuable new digital services that help us in our daily lives.

Yet, at the same time, the ICT sector has a considerable footprint from the energy use, manufacturing of devices and recycling (E-Waste). The goal of this course is to present this footprint, what the impact is on our environment and society, and how it could be lowered and thereby reduce our carbon emissions and impact on global warming.

This course focuses on software development and so-called green software. We raise the question, whether green software even exists, or is it rather simply a marketing concept?

PREREQUISITES

- Understanding of ICT in general, what constitutes our daily digital life
- Understanding energy production and energy usage on a general level
- Ability to read technical and scientific publications

COURSE OBJECTIVES

The course equips learners with the conceptual and technical foundations required to understand, evaluate, and contribute to the design of more sustainable and energy-efficient digital services.

The objective of this course is to provide the students with a structured

understanding of how our digital infrastructure uses energy and material resources and thereby creates a major negative footprint on our society and environment. The course aims to raise awareness of the footprint of ICT and what is being done and what more can be done to support our goal towards a greener future. By the end of the course, learners will have an understanding of the wide impact of ICT resource usage, and how digital services could be built to be more resource efficient.

This course gives the student a holistic understanding of software development, its evolution and current state and impact on environmental sustainability.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Understand the evolution of software engineering
- Understand the environmental impact of software design choices
- Identify potential places for optimising the sustainability of a software product

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus
Introduction
Defining and measuring green software
Reasons software is not always “green”
Ways to write better and “greener” software

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- All material is composed of public technical reports, scientific publications and similar documents, also potentially some online video material

COURSE CONDUCT

The course has an introductory lecture taking the student to the topic and explaining the key concepts. The self-study is based on scientific publications, industry reports and similar documents, and videos in some cases, that take the student deeper into the topic. This self-study is evaluated through multiple-choice quizzes. The grading is based on the quizzes.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 5-6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address conceptual understanding of software engineering from a sustainability perspective and support learners in identifying environmentally relevant software design choices and improvement opportunities in software products and development practices.

INSTRUCTOR

Professor, PhD., Jukka Manner, Aalto University, Department of Information and Communication Engineering (DICE)

Jukka Manner received his MSc. (1999) and PhD. (2004) degrees in computer science from the University of Helsinki. He is a full professor (tenured) of networking technology at Aalto University, Department of Communications and Networking (Comnet). His research and teaching focuses on networking, software and distributed systems, with a strong focus on wireless and mobile networks, transport protocols, energy efficient ICT and cyber security. The past

years his primary research focus has been on the sustainability of ICT at large. He has contributed to standardization of Internet technologies in the IETF since 1999, and was the co-chair of the NSIS working group. He has been principal investigator and project manager for over 15 national and international research projects. He has authored over 200 publications, including eleven IETF RFCs.

High-Performance Python: Profiling and Optimization for HPC

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

Scientific and data-intensive applications written in Python often face performance bottlenecks due to interpreter overhead, limited memory bandwidth, and challenges with parallel execution. This course develops a practical toolbox for analyzing and improving the performance of Python programs for High-Performance Computing (HPC) and data science workloads. Students learn how modern computer architecture affects runtime, how to measure performance with profiling tools, and how to apply optimization techniques, including data layout choices, vectorization, compilation, GPU acceleration, and parallel execution.

PREREQUISITES

- Programming experience in Python (functions, modules, classes, and basic data structures).
- Basic familiarity with the command line (Linux/macOS) and running Python programs from a terminal.
- Introductory knowledge of numerical computing (arrays, basic linear algebra) is beneficial.
- Prior exposure to performance concepts (e.g., timing, big-O notation, or basic computer architecture) is beneficial.

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to

- Explain how CPU, memory, caches, and communication layers affect application performance.

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- Use systematic profiling to locate bottlenecks in CPU time and memory usage,
- Apply data structure choices and vectorization to reduce Python overhead and improve memory efficiency,
- Use compilation approaches to accelerate critical kernels.
- Apply GPU acceleration when appropriate using modern Python ecosystems.
- Parallelize workloads using multiprocessing and distributed computing with Dask.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- measured and explained the performance behavior of Python codes on modern hardware,
- implemented and validated optimizations that improve runtime and/or memory usage for representative workloads,
- used profiling reports to justify optimization choices and to avoid premature or misleading micro-optimizations,

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

Module I: Fundamentals of Computer Systems and Profiling Codes

1.1 Video-lecture: Fundamentals of Computer Systems - Computing Units

1.2 Video-lecture: Fundamentals of Computer Systems - Memory Units

1.3 Video-lecture: Fundamentals of Computer Systems - Communication Layers

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1.4 Video-lecture: Profiling Codes

1.5 Video-lecture: Timing and Julia Set Code

1.6 Video-lecture: Profiling with cProfile

1.7 Video-lecture: Using line_profiler for line-by-line measurements

1.8 Video-lecture: Using memory_profiler to diagnose memory usage

1.9 Video-lecture: Introspecting an existing process with py-spy

1.10 Video-lecture: Bytecode - under the hood with dis

Module II: Data Structures and Methods for HPC

2.1 Video-lecture: Lists and Tuples

2.2 Video-lecture: Lists as dynamic arrays

2.3 Video-lecture: Tuples as static arrays

2.4 Video-lecture: Vectors and matrices - limitations of Python lists

2.5 Video-lecture: The perf tool and low-level profiling

2.6 Video-lecture: Using NumPy for vectorization and addressing the memory fragmentation problem

2.7 Video-lecture: The performance benefits of in-place operations

2.8 Video-lecture: numexpr - optimize NumPy vector expressions

Module III: Using Compilation Techniques and GPUs for Performance Optimization

3.1 Video-lecture: Optimizing using compilers

3.2 Video-lecture: Introduction to Cython

3.3 Video-lecture: Cython annotations to analyze a block of code

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3.4 Video-lecture: Cython - adding type annotations

3.5 Video-lecture: Cython and NumPy

3.6 Video-lecture: Numba - a JIT Python compiler

3.7 Video-lecture: Foreign function interfaces and ctypes

3.8 Video-lecture: Graphics Processing Units (GPUs)

3.9 Video-lecture: Programming the diffusion problem on GPU with PyTorch

Module IV: Using Multi-Processing Techniques for Optimization

4.1 Video-lecture: Introduction to parallel computing with Python

4.2 Video-lecture: An overview of the multiprocessing module

4.3 Video-lecture: Parallelizing a serial code using multiprocessing.Pool

4.5 Video-lecture: Introduction to Dask for parallel computing

4.6 Video-lecture: Parallelizing Python code with dask.delayed

4.7 Video-lecture: Dask arrays - parallelizing NumPy for scientific computing

4.8 Video-lecture: Scaling Python with dask.distributed

4.9 Video-lecture: Dask futures - task execution and dynamic workflows

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- I. Ozsvald and M. Gorelick, High Performance Python (2nd ed.), O'Reilly Media.

COURSE CONDUCT

The course is delivered online with recorded video-lectures. Each module includes short quizzes to reinforce key ideas. Students are expected to run experiments on their own machines or in provided cloud environments (e.g., Google Colab for GPU content). Passing the course requires completion of all module quizzes.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6-7: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address advanced knowledge of performance behavior in Python workloads and support learners in profiling, analyzing bottlenecks, implementing and validating optimizations, and justifying performance-related design decisions in HPC and data-intensive contexts.

INSTRUCTOR

Prof. Stefano Markidis is a full professor at KTH Royal Institute of Technology. His work focuses on high-performance computing, parallel programming, and performance optimization for scientific and data-intensive applications. His research and teaching span GPU computing, scalable algorithms, and tools for analyzing and improving code performance on modern heterogeneous architectures, as well as quantum computing and quantum machine learning. He has led and contributed to research projects and training activities, helping students and researchers build practical skills in profiling, optimization, and efficient Python programming for real-world computational workloads.

Introduction to Computer Networking

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course provides an introduction to the principles and practice of computer networking. Network components, layered architecture, addressing, routing, reliable communication, congestion control and flow control are explored. The services provided by computer networks and the development of distributed applications using these services are detailed. Modern topics such as software-defined networking, data center networks, HTTP/QUIC, and CDNs are also introduced.

PREREQUISITES

- Basic mathematics, probability and statistics.
- Fundamental knowledge of computer systems.
- Being comfortable with at least one high-level programming language (preferably Python).

COURSE OBJECTIVES

By the end of the course, the students will:

- Understand and explain key concepts related to computer networks.
- Know the principles of data transfer in computer networks and internetworking.
- Evaluate basic network performance metrics such as delay, loss, and throughput.
- Understand the operation of fundamental protocols.
- Develop distributed applications using socket programming.

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- Know the basic principles required to set up and operate a computer network.
- Recognize trending topics such as SDN, data centers, and HTTP/QUIC.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

By the end of the course the students will be able to:

- Identify the constituent elements of computer networks, such as hosts, switching devices, links, and protocols.
- Define the layered architecture of the Internet protocol stack and the roles of each layer.
- Explain the basic services provided by computer networks.
- Analyze simple network scenarios to assess performance factors such as delay, loss, and throughput.
- Explain basic mechanisms such as packet switching, reliable communication, addressing, routing, flow control, and congestion control.
- Develop distributed applications using the socket API.
- Identify and describe basic link-layer technologies.
- Identify and explain the architecture and technologies used in data center networks.
- Explain the basics of software-defined networks.

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

List of topics (approx. one-hour per main topic):

1. Introduction to Computer Networks
 - a. Hosts, Routers, Switches, Middleboxes

- b. WAN, LAN, PAN
 - c. Circuit Switching / Packet Switching
 - d. Layered Architecture
- 2. Distributed Applications
 - a. Client-Server
 - b. Peer-to-Peer
 - c. RDMA
- Recap & Quiz
- 3. Network Service
 - a. Addressing Network Devices – IPv4/DNS
 - b. Service Endpoints (sockets)
 - c. Delay-Loss-Throughput / QoS / QoE
 - d. Reliable Data Transfer / TCP
 - e. Best-Effort Data Transfer / UDP
- 4. Developing Network Applications
 - a. TCP
 - b. UDP
- Recap & Quiz
- 5. Addressing
 - a. IPv4, IPv6
 - b. DHCP
 - c. NAT
- 6. Routing
 - a. Intra-AS

- b. Inter-AS
 - Recap & Quiz
- 7. Reliable Communication
 - a. Basic mechanisms: Checksum, Acknowledgment, Sequence Number, Timer
 - b. Stop-and-Wait
 - c. Pipelining: Go-Back-N, Selective-Repeat
- 8. Flow Control and Congestion Control
 - Recap & Quiz
- 9. Local Area Networks
 - a. Multiple Access Protocols
 - b. Link Layer Addressing and ARP
 - c. Ethernet, Wi-Fi
 - d. VPN
- 10. Data Center Networks
 - Recap & Quiz
- 11. Software Defined Networks
 - a. Controller, Switches
 - b. OpenFlow
 - c. P4
- 12. Modern Web and Transport Layer Evolution
 - a. HTTPv2, HTTPv3
 - b. CDN

- Recap & Quiz

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- Jim Kurose, Keith Ross, “Computer Networking: A Top-Down Approach”, 9th Edition, isbn: 978-0135429334, Pearson, 2025.

COURSE CONDUCT

Each topic will be covered in approximately 1-hour sessions.

After every two topics (approximately 2 hours), a short recap will be provided, followed by a multiple-choice quiz to evaluate students’ understanding of key concepts and reinforce their learning.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 5-6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address foundational-to-intermediate knowledge of computer networking concepts, protocols, and architectures, while supporting learners in explaining networking mechanisms, comparing design options, and reasoning about core communication-system behaviors.

INSTRUCTOR

Altan Koçyiğit received his B.Sc., M.Sc., and Ph.D. degrees from the Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering at METU in 1993, 1997, and 2001, respectively. He is currently serving as a professor at the Informatics Institute at METU, where he has been a faculty member since 2002. His research focuses on networking, data science, software engineering, and parallel and distributed systems.

Introduction to GPU Computing and CUDA Programming

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course provides a comprehensive introduction to GPU computing and CUDA programming. Students will explore modern GPU architecture, including streaming multiprocessors, memory hierarchies, and the parallel execution model. The curriculum covers CUDA programming fundamentals, thread organization, memory management strategies, and performance optimization techniques. Topics include memory coalescing, warp divergence, control flow optimization, and floating-point considerations. Students will learn to identify GPU-suitable problems, understand performance bottlenecks through profiling concepts, and apply optimization strategies. The course concludes with advanced topics including streams, concurrent execution, and multi-GPU systems, preparing students for high-performance parallel computing applications

PREREQUISITES

- Proficiency in C or C++ programming
- Understanding of pointers, memory management, and data structures
- Basic knowledge of computer architecture (CPU, memory, cache hierarchy)

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to

1. Explain the architectural differences between CPUs and GPUs and identify appropriate computational problems for GPU acceleration
2. Describe GPU hardware organization including streaming multiprocessors, CUDA cores, warps, and memory hierarchy

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3. Design CUDA programs using the proper thread organization, grid/block configurations, and kernel launch parameters
4. Analyse memory access patterns and apply optimization techniques including coalescing and effective use of shared memory
5. Identify performance bottlenecks related to warp divergence, control flow, and memory bandwidth limitations
6. Apply optimization strategies to improve GPU code performance including occupancy tuning and reduction of branch divergence
7. Utilise profiling concepts and debugging strategies to diagnose and resolve common GPU programming issues
8. Compare different memory types and select appropriate memory spaces for specific use cases
9. Understand advanced GPU programming concepts including streams, asynchronous execution, and multi-GPU systems

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Acquired comprehensive knowledge of GPU architecture, CUDA programming model, and parallel execution principles
- Understood thread organization, memory hierarchy, and the mapping between hardware and software abstractions in CUDA
- Analysed performance optimization techniques including memory coalescing, warp efficiency, and occupancy maximization
- Evaluated code performance considerations including control flow divergence, memory access patterns, and floating-point precision
- Gained familiarity with profiling strategies, debugging approaches, and best practices for GPU application development

- Explored advanced concepts including streams, concurrent execution, and multi-GPU programming architectures

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

Introduction to GPUs and Parallel Programming
Computer Architecture and GPU Fundamentals
CUDA Programming Model
Thread Organization and Execution
Memory Hierarchy and Management
Memory Access Patterns and Optimization
Warps, Control Flow, and Divergence
Performance Optimization Techniques
Floating Point Considerations and Atomic Operations
Profiling, Debugging
Advanced Topics: Streams, Events, and Multi-GPU

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- David B. Kirk and Wen-mei W. Hwu, Izzat El Hajj, “Programming Massively Parallel Processors: A Hands-on Approach – 4th Edition”, Morgan Kaufman, ISBN-13: 978-0323912310.
- Jason Sanders, Edward Kandrot, “CUDA by Example: An Introduction to General-Purpose GPU Programming”, Addison Wesley, ISBN-13: 978-0131387683.
- S. Cook, “CUDA Programming: A Developer's Guide to Parallel Computing with GPUs”, ISBN-13: 978-0124159334
- Rob Farber, “CUDA Application Design and Development”, ISBN-13: 978-0123884268.

COURSE CONDUCT

Each chapter begins with an explanation of the underlying theoretical concepts and progresses to hands-on coding exercises. After each chapter, a short multiple-choice quiz will be used to evaluate students' understanding of the key concepts and reinforce their learning.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6-7: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address advanced knowledge of GPU architecture and CUDA programming and support learners in analyzing performance bottlenecks, applying optimization strategies, and evaluating implementation choices in parallel GPU applications.

INSTRUCTOR

Alptekin Temizel is a Professor at the Graduate School of Informatics at the Middle East Technical University (METU), Turkey. He earned his Ph.D. from the Center for Vision, Speech and Signal Processing (CVSSP) at the University of Surrey, UK, in 2006. He is the Principal Investigator of the Deep Learning and Computer Vision Research Lab and serves as an NVIDIA Deep Learning Institute Certified Instructor and University Ambassador. From 2016 to 2017, he was on sabbatical at the University of Birmingham, UK. He also collaborates with various companies on the design and deployment of computer vision and AI systems. His research focuses on computer vision, machine learning, deep learning, and GPU computing.

Introduction to Information Systems

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course provides an overview of the important role of information systems in a global business world. The content explores the interdisciplinary nature of information systems, and highlights various aspects such as technology, organization, management, strategy, and operations. Various digital technologies and applications of information systems are presented, considering the impact of the high speed of development in this field. The role of information systems in organizations are explored for use cases such as resource planning, supply chain management, decision making, and customer management.

PREREQUISITES

- Basic understanding of computing and business concepts.

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to

- Understand basic concepts of information systems
- Explore the interdisciplinary nature of information systems
- See various applications of information systems
- Explore the different types of information systems in organizations

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Understood information systems from a socio-technical point of view
- Classified various types of information systems from different perspectives
- Evaluated information systems related issues in organisations
- Compared enterprise information systems

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

Information Systems and Business

The Interdisciplinary Nature of Information Systems

The Role of Information Systems in Organizations

Strategy and Information Systems

The Components of Information Systems

Decision Support Systems

Business and Data Analytics

Resource Planning Systems

Customer Relationship Management

Supply Chain Management

Knowledge Management

Developing Information Systems

Project Management

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

115

Deliverable D3.1 ACHIEVE Self
Standing Modules: Market analysis and
curriculum design

Project: ACHIEVE (101190015)

- Laudon, K., and Laudon, J. (2022), Management Information Systems: Managing the Digital Firm, 17th edition, Pearson
- Valacich, J., Schneider, C., Hashim, M. (2022), Information Systems Today: Managing in the Digital World, 9th edition, Pearson

COURSE CONDUCT

Each chapter provides explanations of the fundamental concepts and their practical implications. After each chapter, a short multiple-choice quiz will be used to evaluate students' understanding of the key concepts and reinforce their learning.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 5-6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address structured knowledge of information systems in organizational and socio-technical contexts, and support learners in classifying, comparing, and evaluating information-system roles and issues across business domains.

INSTRUCTOR

Prof. P. Erhan Eren is a faculty member of the Information Systems Department and also the chair of Data Informatics Department at Informatics Institute, METU. He received his B.S. degree in Electrical and Electronics Engineering at Bilkent University. He was a teaching and research assistant during his graduate studies at University of Rochester, where he received his M.S. and Ph.D. degrees. During his Ph.D. studies, he also served as a technical consultant for image/video processing projects at Eastman Kodak Research Labs, Rochester, NY. He was a Senior Staff Research Engineer at Motorola Corporate Research Labs, Schaumburg, IL, and worked there for seven years.

His research interests and graduate-level teaching subjects include data-driven organizations, big data, cloud computing, artificial intelligence applications, digital transformation, and management information systems.

Modern Cloud Architectures – Virtualization, Docker and Kubernetes

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course explores the principles of virtualized cloud computing architectures based on containerization and orchestration, bridging theoretical foundations with hands-on implementation. Starting with cloud architecture, learners will analyze and contrast VM-based and container-based virtualization techniques. The course then dives into containerization and orchestration, covering Docker for lightweight application packaging and Kubernetes for orchestrating scalable containerized workloads.

Through practical labs, deploying real applications in Docker and Kubernetes, students will compare traditional virtualization with modern cloud-native approaches. By the end, learners will understand how to design resilient, scalable systems while evaluating the performance, security, and operational implications of different architectures. Ideal for professionals seeking to leverage cloud technologies for efficient, agile cloud infrastructure.

PREREQUISITES

- General understanding of distributed computing and networking concepts
- Good command of Linux including the command line
- Some prior experience in developing and/or deploying distributed applications (web servers, application servers, database servers)

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to:

- Analyze the fundamental principles of cloud computing and virtualization to explain how abstraction layers enable scalable, elastic infrastructure
- Apply cloud architecture paradigms to design resilient, cost-efficient solutions for real-world use cases
- Evaluate trade-offs between different cloud deployment models based on business and technical requirements
- Design containerized applications using Docker, considering performance, security, and scalability constraints
- Orchestrate containerized workloads with Kubernetes, including scaling strategies, networking, and fault tolerance mechanisms
- Justify architectural decisions by comparing traditional systems with cloud-native approaches

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Configured and managed virtualized environments by installing, resizing, and maintaining virtual machines, while practicing basic system administration tasks such as snapshotting and resource allocation.
- Containerized applications by deploying WordPress using Docker, experimenting with containerization concepts such as image layering, resource isolation, and lightweight deployment workflows.
- Deployed cloud-native applications using Kubernetes, experimenting with design choices and tradeoffs of scalable cloud architectures.
- Evaluated trade-offs between virtualization, and containerization by comparing the performance, scalability, and operational complexity of different deployment approaches for the same application (WordPress).
- Conducted a full cloud-native deployment project using a microservice-based application, paying attention to manageability, elasticity and observability aspects.

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

Introduction (2 hours)

- Cloud as a service paradigm: From products to services
- The capacity problem solved: Fixed vs. dynamic scaling (vertical vs. horizontal)
- Cloud computing defined: Key characteristics
- Cloud provider landscape: Market leaders and service tiers
- Public vs. private vs. hybrid/multi-cloud: Trade-offs and real-world adoption
- Business expectations vs. challenges: What companies gain and struggle with

Part I – Virtualization: How cloud enables abstraction and efficiency

Virtualization defined: Analogies and core principles

- Storage virtualization: Copy-on-write, overlay filesystems, and distributed storage
- Network virtualization: Why clouds need it and SDN's role
- Virtual machines: Why they matter and their trade-offs
- Containers: Lightweight virtualization technologies
- Practical exercise: deploying WordPress in Virtualbox, including volume resizing, snapshotting and host-to-VM communication

Part II – Cloud Architecture: Definitions, paradigms, and key components

- Cloud Architecture: Core Definitions and Paradigms
- Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS): The Building Block
- Data Storage in the Cloud
- Cloud Networking
- Application Delivery and Resilience
- Architectural Patterns and Anti-Patterns

Part III – Containers and Docker: Lightweight application deployment

- Why containers? Developer-centric benefits and OS-level features
- Docker's architecture: Container runtime, registry, and orchestration gaps
- Docker images/layering: Why multi-layered images matter
- Building containers: Dockerfiles, volumes, and host integration
- Docker vs. cloud: Clarifying misconceptions
- Advanced workflows: multi-container setups, networking, and security
- Practical exercise: writing a Dockerfile and building a Docker container from scratch, host-to-container communication.

Part IV – Orchestration and Kubernetes: cloud-native deployment

- Why orchestration? Problems Docker solves and leaves unsolved
- Kubernetes architecture: Control plane vs. worker nodes, and the role of etcd
- Pods and controllers: Pods as atomic units, and controllers for controlled scaling
- Deployments and rolling updates: Zero-downtime deployments and health checks

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- Services and networking: Cluster-internal DNS, Ingress, and external access
- Networking deep dive: Pod-to-pod communication, CNI plugins, and security policies
- Practical exercise: deploying a ready-made image in Kubernetes, exposing it to the outside world, elasticity issues of this image, redesigning the image to support elasticity.

Part V – Cloud-native microservice application management

- Final project: cloud-native deployment, manageability and observability of a microservice-based application

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- Docker: Up & Running; Shipping Reliable Containers in Production. Sean P Kane and Karl Matthias, O'Reilly Media, 2023.
- Kubernetes: Up and Running: Dive Into the Future of Infrastructure. Brendan Burns, Joe Beda, Kelsey Hightower and Lachlan Evenson, O'Reilly Media, 2022.

COURSE CONDUCT

Initial Assessment: The course starts with a brief knowledge check to confirm prerequisites. **Interactive Learning:** Short questions are integrated into each lecture to reinforce understanding. **Chapter Reinforcement:** Each chapter concludes with a quiz, assessing both theoretical and practical knowledge. **Hands-On Practice:** Practical sessions are included within each chapter to apply learned concepts. Learners are provided with solution walkthroughs, hints and guidance and/or structured rubrics to help them self-assess their work.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6-7: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address advanced knowledge of virtualization, containerization, and orchestration and support learners in analyzing architectural trade-offs, applying cloud-native design concepts, and evaluating resilience, scalability, and operational implications of modern cloud infrastructures.

INSTRUCTOR

Guillaume Pierre – Professor of Computer Science at the University of Rennes

Network Security

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course will cover fundamentals of network security. The course provides a strong foundation in network security. The following topics are covered: encryption techniques, key management and authentication, hashing, public key cryptography, web security, TCP/IP, DDoS attacks, DNS security.

PREREQUISITES

Students are expected to have working knowledge on computer networks.

COURSE OBJECTIVES

- Understand security concepts in Network Security
- Understand security threats, and the security services and mechanisms to counter them
- Comprehend relevant cryptographic techniques
- Comprehend and apply security services and mechanisms in the network protocol stack
- Comprehend web security services and mechanisms

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Identified and classified network security threats and vulnerabilities
- Explained and evaluated authentication and key management mechanisms

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- Analysed security mechanisms in TCP/IP and routing protocols
- Assessed web security architectures and protocols
- Evaluated defences against DoS and DDoS attacks
- Used basic network defence and monitoring tools

COURSE OUTLINE

- Fundamentals of Network & Security
- Common Threats
- Cryptography overview and concepts
- Public Key Cryptography: Digital Signatures, Encryption, And Key Exchange
- Application Layer Security
- Web Application Security
- Transport Layer Security
- Transport Layer Attacks
- Network Layer Security
- TCP/IP and its security
- DDoS attacks and Routing security
- Data Link layer Security
- Physical Security
- Security in Mobile Platforms

TEXTBOOKS AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- W. Stallings, Cryptography and Network Security: Principles and Practice, 8th ed., Pearson (Global Edition), 2021

- R. J. Anderson, Security Engineering: A Guide to Building Dependable Distributed Systems, 3rd ed., Wiley, 2020
- J. Katz and Y. Lindell, Introduction to Modern Cryptography, Revised 3rd ed., Chapman & Hall/CRC Press, 2025

COURSE CONDUCT

- Lectures covering theoretical foundations
- Practical demonstrations and case studies
- Analysis of real-world attack and defense scenarios

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address applied knowledge of network security principles, threats, and protection mechanisms, and support learners in analyzing risks, comparing mitigation strategies, and evaluating security controls in networked systems.

INSTRUCTOR

Prof. Nazife Baykal is a Professor at the Graduate School of Informatics, Middle East Technical University (METU), where she has been a faculty member since 2004. She received her B.Sc. in Mathematics and her M.Sc. and Ph.D. in Computer Engineering from METU. Prof. Baykal's research spans information systems, cybersecurity, data mining, machine learning, health informatics, and critical infrastructure protection. She has published extensively in leading international journals and conferences and has supervised a large number of Master's and Ph.D. theses in areas including cybersecurity, privacy-preserving systems, malware detection, medical informatics, and data analytics. She has held several senior academic and administrative roles at METU, including Director of the Graduate School of Informatics, Head of the Cybersecurity Department, Rector's Advisor, and Campus Administrator. Prof. Baykal has also contributed to national and international research projects and holds a

patent related to information security assessment. Her work has significantly influenced academic research, policy development, and applied systems in cybersecurity and informatics.

Network systems with edge or cloud datacenters

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course explores advancements in datacenter technology, covering topics like Layer 2 technologies (Ethernet vs. Infiniband), reconfigurable topologies, congestion control, virtualization, interconnects, and energy efficiency. Students will examine scalable datacenter architectures, from edge to massive cloud setups, emphasizing latency, power efficiency, and machine learning applications with unprecedented I/O demands. Through this, students will gain insights into managing geographically distributed networks, multi-tenancy, and the role of Software-Defined-Networking (SDN) and in-network computing. By the course end, students will understand the key trends and challenges shaping modern datacenter evolution.

PREREQUISITES

- Good knowledge of Internetworking.

COURSE OBJECTIVES

Gain a comprehensive view of the modern data center evolution and understand its drivers, as well as the challenges ahead.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

After passing the course, the student should be able to:

- explain and analyse methods for interconnecting networks and end host

devices in a data centre including emerging aspects of topology, technologies for link layer and protocols

- explain and analyse methods to operate virtualized multi-tenant networks in data centres.
- explain and analyse methods and concepts related to programmable networks including aspects of Software-Defined Networking, routing, packet forwarding and congestion control.
- explain and analyse concepts and applications related to in network computing and support for machine learning applications.
- explain and analyse aspects related to energy efficiency of different data centre technology.

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

- The development of data centre including network speeds, scale, geographic spread, multitenancy, and tongue I/O applications.
- Link layer technology for the data centre of the next generation with a focus on Ethernet products compared with specialised Infiniband.
- The complexity of managing networks of geographically dispersed data centres and their related energy consumption aspects.
- The balance between compact edge data centres and their expansive cloud counterparts, designed to optimize latency.
- The bases of the software defined the paradigm and protocol-independent programmable networks.
- Relating the above infrastructure aspects to concrete workloads focusing on new machine learning applications with heavy I/O requirements.

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- How these applications are shaping data centre design and operation, pushing the boundaries of what is possible.
- Aspects of data centre networking related to multitenancy, its requirements, and the role of virtualization technologies in mitigating potential disruptions.

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- Course notes and research papers.

COURSE CONDUCT

Lectures covering the topics in the course outline. After each chapter, a short multiple-choice quiz will be used to evaluate students' understanding of the key concepts and reinforce their learning.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6-7: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address advanced knowledge of networked systems integrating edge and cloud datacentres and support learners in analysing distributed architectures, evaluating system-level trade-offs, and reasoning about performance, scalability, and service placement choices.

INSTRUCTOR

Associate Professor Marco Chiesa is associate professor at KTH Royal Institute of Technology within the School of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science. His research spans computer networking and AI-driven software systems, with a particular focus on Internet architectures, AI data centres, protocol design, and the intersection of security, privacy, and automation.

Recently, he have been exploring AI-based code generation and verification as a foundation for building more reliable, secure, and explainable systems, combining formal methods with machine learning to advance intelligent infrastructure, and applications to networking.

Parallel Programming in Rust

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

Parallel programming is a concise and fast-paced introduction to parallel programming for performance-focused computing intended for existing developers who are accustomed to working with languages that do not prioritize performance and parallelism. This introduction is done in Rust which provides both an excellent developer experience, and excellent single-thread performance, as well as a vast array of parallelization techniques. The course covers both an introduction to fast, safe Rust, as well as simple threading techniques, advanced threading with Crossbeam/flume, automated work-stealing parallelization of Rayon, and GPU acceleration through cudarc. An introduction to CUDA architecture and programming model is also included.

PREREQUISITES

- Understanding of fundamental programming concepts
- Proficiency in at least one programming language
- An understanding of mathematical concepts at a university freshman level (i.e. fundamentals of calculus and discrete algebra)

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to

- Understand and explain basic and intermediate concepts in parallel programming
- Develop intermediate Rust proficiency
- Solve intermediate parallel programming tasks using the right tools in Rust.
- Easily adapt to domain-specific tooling and challenges.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Written small but functional and high-performance implementations of key algorithms in Rust using suitable tools.
- Had experience in necessary tooling and environment setup for high performance and parallel computing
- Learned the fundamentals of parallel problem decomposition

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

- Setting up the Rust environment and making use of the cargo to manage projects and dependencies.
- Introductory Rust: variables and mutability, control flow and functions, arrays, tuples, and structs.
- Quality code in Rust: tests and documentation.
- The Ownership model of Rust, references, and slices.
- Rust's rich type system: advanced struct use cases, enumerations, pattern-matching, and conditional lets. Generics.

- Rust lifetimes, static, specific, and their use.
- Rust traits and how they compare to traditional OOP constructs.
- Rust standard library support for:
 - Errors (and the Anyhow crate)
 - Basic data structures
 - Command line parameters (and the clap crate)
 - Working with files
- Closures and iterators in Rust
- Rust's 'pointer' types: Rc, Box, and Arc, and the dyn keyword.
- Rust for larger projects: packages, crates, workspaces, and build.rs
- Classic threading in Rust
- Ergonomic threading with channels and scopes with Crossbeam and Flume.
- Effortless work-stealing parallelization with Rayon
- CUDA fundamentals: kernels, dimensions, indices, and tiles.
- CUDA libraries and optimizations.
- Running CUDA kernels in Rust with cudarc

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- Klabnik, Steve, and Carol Nichols. The Rust programming language. No Starch Press, 2023. (and modern online iterations).
- Rust by Example, <https://doc.rust-lang.org/rust-by-example/>
- Rustlings, <https://rustlings.rust-lang.org/>
- Relevant crate documentation available on docs.rs

COURSE CONDUCT

At the end of each chapter of the course, students will be given exercise problems that they will work to independently solve before they are evaluated at the start of the next chapter. The results of these evaluations will track each student's progress, and this start-of-chapter session will be used to make sure that everyone understands the solution to these exercises before progressing.

Each chapter will be preceded by assigned reading from the reference documentation. Then, at the start of the class period an overview of this material will be presented. This overview's key purpose is to identify weaknesses in the student's understanding of the material and to remedy these weaknesses. This is followed by a series of exercises that are partially done by the student themselves and partially demonstrated by the instructor.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6-7: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address advanced knowledge of parallel programming concepts and Rust-based implementation patterns, and support learners in designing and implementing concurrent/parallel solutions while evaluating correctness, safety, and performance trade-offs.

INSTRUCTOR

Prof. Veljko Petrović

Prof. Dušan Gajić

Prof. Dinu Dragan

Nikola Vukić

Branislav Ristić

Performance evaluation of computing and networked systems

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

The performance of computing and communication systems depends on the availability of many shared resources, from the wireless spectrum in mobile networks to the computing units of the data centers. The design of these systems therefore requires a basic understanding of how the amount of resources, the utilization, the patterns and control of the access to the resources affect the performance the users experience.

Queuing theory is the basic tool for performance evaluation and dimensioning of resource sharing systems such as communication networks, computing systems, road traffic and transport systems, and other resource sharing systems, like digital health services. This course covers basic tools that help the understanding of how the performance these systems depend on the system capabilities and the system load, with the objective to support system design. The course treats queuing systems with an emphasis on the classical, basic Markovian models. The theory is illustrated by problems drawn from communication and computing.

PREREQUISITES

- Good knowledge of basic probability theory and some understanding of stochastic processes
- Basic knowledge of communication networks or computing systems.

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to

- explain the basic theory of Markov-processes and apply the theory to model queuing systems,
- derive and use analytic models of of Markovian queuing systems, queuing networks and also some simpler non-Markovian systems,
- define queuing models of communication or computer systems, and derive the performance of these systems,

in order to be able to carry out mathematical modeling-based performance evaluation of communication, computing, or other resource sharing systems.

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- evaluated the performance of simple resource sharing systems with the help of mathematical models
- constructed queuing theory models for networked systems and computing systems
- understood some basic trade-offs of the performance of resource sharing systems

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

- Discrete and continuous time Markov chains, birth-death processes, and the Poisson process.
- Basic terminology of queuing systems, Kendall's notation and Little's theorem.

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- Markovian waiting systems with one or more servers, and systems with infinite as well as finite buffers and finite user populations (M/M/*).
- Loss systems according to Erlang and Engset.
- Systems with general service distributions (M/G/1).
- Open queuing networks.

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- L. Kleinrock, Queueing Systems, Volume 1: Theory, Wiley, 1975 (well known, for engineers)
- M. Harchol-Balter, Performance modeling and design of computer systems, Cambridge, 2014 (new, entertaining)
- L. Lakatos, L. Szeidl and M. Telek, (2019). Introduction to Queueing Systems with Telecommunication Applications, Springer, 2019 (similar to this course)

COURSE CONDUCT

The main lectures cover the theory of queuing systems. Short lectures address numerical examples. After each chapter, a short multiple-choice quiz will be used to evaluate students' understanding of the key concepts and reinforce their learning.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6-7: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address advanced knowledge of stochastic and queueing-based performance modeling and support learners in constructing analytical models, evaluating system performance, and reasoning about trade-offs in computing and communication systems.

INSTRUCTOR

Prof. Viktoria Fodor, KTH Royal Institute of Technology. Prof. Fodor is professor in Communication Networks at the Department for Network and Systems Engineering at the School of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science. She is teaching courses on stochastic network modeling and performance evaluation of communication networks as well as on computer systems. Her research interest includes modeling and evaluation of communication networks and services, with recent focus on wireless sensor networks, multimedia networks, edge computing and collaborative learning.

Platforms and Systems for Cloud Computing: A Data Perspective

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course covers several applied concepts and techniques about modern data management and computation technologies used in cloud environments. It covers cloud database fundamentals, including relational cloud databases and scaling techniques for performance and availability. Students explore big data ecosystems such as Hadoop, HDFS, and MapReduce for large-scale data processing. The course also presents container technologies (Docker, Podman) and container orchestration platforms (Kubernetes, OpenShift). Finally, it introduces parallel computation models based on message passing, with a focus on the Message Passing Interface (MPI) for high-performance distributed computing.

PREREQUISITES

- Proficiency in at least one programming language (C, C++ or Python, Java)
- Good knowledge about computer network fundamentals
- Basic understanding of cloud computing and platforms
- Good knowledge about databases and associated concepts

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to

- Conceive architectures for Cloud Databases
- Know and use large data processing techniques in the cloud
- Use distributed cloud filesystems and logical storage

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- Manage container orchestration platforms for cloud systems
- Apply parallel computation models for cloud processing

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- Basic understanding of the architecture of Cloud Databases
- Knowledge of large data processing techniques in the cloud
- Explored distributed cloud filesystems and logical storage
- Knowledge about managing container orchestration platforms for cloud systems
- Evaluated parallel computation models for cloud processing

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

- Introduction to Cloud Databases
- Relational Databases in the Cloud
- Scaling techniques for Cloud Databases
- Hadoop BigData and Cloud File Systems: HDFS
- Techniques for large data processing in the cloud: Map Reduce
- Container Runtimes: Docker and Podman
- Container Orchestration (Kubernetes and OpenShift)
- Parallel Computation Models based on message passing
- Message Passing Interface (MPI)

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- Tom White, Hadoop: The Definitive Guide, O'Reilly, ISBN: 978-0-596-52197-4, 2011
- Jimmy Lin, Chris Dyer, Data-Intensive Text Processing with MapReduce, Morgan and Claypool Publishers, ISBN-10: 1608453421, 2010.
- M J QUINN. Parallel Programming in C with MPI and OpenMP, McGraw Hill, 2004.
- B. WILKINSON, C.M. ALLEN. Parallel Programming: Techniques and Applications Using Networked Workstations and Parallel Computers, Prentice Hall, 1999.
- Scott Surovich, Marc Boorshtein, Kubernetes and Docker - An Enterprise Guide: Effectively containerize applications, integrate enterprise systems, and scale applications in your enterprise, Packt Publishing, ISBN 978-1839213403, 2020
- Wendy Neu, Vlad Vlasceanu, Andy Oram & Sam Alapati, An Introduction to Cloud Databases, O'Reilly Media
- Rukmani Gopalan, The Cloud Data Lake: A Guide to Building Robust Cloud Data Architecture, O'Reilly Media

COURSE CONDUCT

Each chapter provides explanations of the fundamental concepts and their practical implications.

After each chapter, a short multiple-choice quiz will be used to evaluate students' understanding of the key concepts and reinforce their learning.

Each chapter begins with an explanation of the underlying theoretical concepts and progresses to hands-on practical exercises.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6-7: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address advanced applied knowledge of cloud data platforms, distributed storage, large-scale data processing, orchestration platforms, and parallel computation models, and support learners in conceiving architectures and evaluating platform choices for cloud-based data systems.

INSTRUCTOR

DARABANT Sergiu Adrian is a professor and PhD advisor at the Department of Computer Science, Babeş-Bolyai University, where he teaches and conducts research in distributed systems, cloud computing, databases, and distributed computing. His academic work focuses on scalable data processing, high-performance computing, and Infrn-native technologies. He is actively involved in curriculum development and research projects that bridge theoretical foundations with practical applications in large-scale and distributed computing systems.

Adrian Sterca is an associate professor of Computer Science at Babes-Bolyai University, Romania. He teaches Web Programming, Advanced Networking and Formal modelling of concurrent processes at bachelor level and master level. His research interests include networking, web automation, parallel programming, video streaming.

Virginia Niculescu is an Associate Professor in the Department of Computer Science at **Babeş-Bolyai University**, where she has developed her academic career around teaching and research in parallel and distributed computing. She has taught a wide range of courses from *Parallel and Distributed Programming* to *Models in Parallel Programming* and is involved in the *High-Performance Computing and Big Data Analytics* master programme. Over time her work has evolved from foundational research in parallel computation

and programming models into interdisciplinary high-performance computing applications, collaborating in international conferences and engaging students in both theoretical and applied aspects of computing.

Horea Grebla is a lecturer in Computer Science at Babes-Bolyai University, Romania. He teaches Advanced Databases, Architectures of Cloud Systems, Cloud Databases at bachelor level and master level. His research interests include distributed systems, databases and data analytics.

Quantum computing: A Software Engineering perspective

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course provides a comprehensive introduction to quantum computing and quantum programming models, focusing on both theoretical foundations and practical implementation. Students will explore the fundamental differences between classical and quantum computation, the main challenges of quantum technologies, and promising application domains. The course covers two major quantum programming paradigms-quantum annealing and gate-based computation-through lectures and hands-on sessions. Advanced approaches such as QAOA and quantum machine learning are introduced, together with an overview of the quantum software lifecycle. By the end of the course, students will be able to design, implement, and evaluate quantum programs using modern frameworks and platforms.

PREREQUISITES

- Understanding of fundamental programming concepts
- Proficiency in at least one programming language (e.g. Python)

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully completing the course, students will be able to:

- Understand and explain the fundamental principles of quantum computing
- Compare classical and quantum computational models
- Identify challenges and opportunities in quantum technologies
- Apply different quantum programming models to solve computational

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problems

- Design and implement quantum algorithms using contemporary frameworks
- Evaluate quantum solutions in terms of performance and applicability

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, students will have:

- Developed a conceptual understanding of quantum computation and its paradigms
- Implemented quantum programs using both quantum annealing and gate-based models
- Formulated optimization problems using the QUBO model and executed them on quantum annealers
- Designed and tested basic quantum algorithms (e.g., Deutsch-Jozsa, Grover, Shor)
- Employed advanced techniques such as QAOA and quantum machine learning
- Analyzed the quantum software lifecycle from design to testing within complex system

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

1. Introduction to Quantum Computing
 - Peculiarities of quantum computation vs. classical computation
 - Key challenges in quantum technologies
 - Promising application domains

- Quantum programming models overview
- From classical bits to qubits
- 2. Quantum Annealing Programming Model
 - The quantum annealing paradigm
 - D-Wave Ocean framework
 - QUBO model
 - Mapping and executing QUBO models on quantum annealers
 - QUBO formulation techniques
 - Practical examples and exercises
- 3. Gate-Based Quantum Programming Model
 - Gate model paradigm
 - Platforms for gate-based quantum computing
 - Quantum gates and circuits
 - Fundamental algorithms: Deutsch–Jozsa, quantum teleportation, superdense coding
 - Advanced algorithms: Grover’s and Shor’s algorithms
 - Quantum software design using composed algorithms (k-coloring case study)
 - High-level programming frameworks (e.g., Classiq)
- 4. Advanced Quantum Programming Approaches
 - Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA)
 - Quantum machine learning
- 5. Quantum Software Lifecycle

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- Design and modeling
- Compilation and execution
- Error correction and mitigation
- Analysis and testing
- Integration of quantum software in complex systems

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- Quantum Computation and Quantum Information. Cambridge University Press.
- D-Wave Systems Documentation and Ocean SDK Tutorials
- IBM Quantum and Qiskit Documentation
- Other materials to be defined

COURSE CONDUCT

The course combines theoretical lectures with practical hands-on sessions. Each topic is introduced through conceptual explanations followed by concrete examples and programming exercises. Some lectures conclude with assignments that students are expected to complete before the following session. Student evaluation is based on quizzes at the end of selected modules and practical programming assignments.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6-7: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address specialized knowledge of quantum computing from a software engineering viewpoint and support learners in analyzing development

workflows, comparing implementation approaches, and reasoning about software lifecycle and engineering constraints in an emerging domain.

INSTRUCTOR

Prof. Elisabetta Di Nitto, is Full Professor at Politecnico di Milano. Elisabetta's expertise lies in the area of software engineering and, in particular, of large-scale, open, service-oriented systems with a special attention to the techniques to make these systems self-adaptable to the changes in the environment and in the performances of its distributed components, and to enable them to identify and incorporate new components at runtime. Recently, she has been focusing on supporting the development, deployment and operation of data-intensive applications and on Cloud Computing and, in particular on how to design applications that can run on multiple clouds in order to limit vendor lock-in and to increase availability and reliability of such applications. Currently, she is focusing on quantum computing and on how to exploit it to support the development of complex systems.

Social Network Analysis

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

Social network analysis is a core methodology utilising graph theory, algebra, statistics, sociometry and psychometry for a diverse field of applications. This course is intended to introduce to students how to extract information contained in a network to measure and characterize them. Most commonly used software and Python packages for measuring and displaying network data will be introduced with practical examples, focusing on specific applications in different fields.

PREREQUISITES

- Understanding linear algebra and discrete mathematics
- Proficiency in Python

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to

- explain key terminology of the social network analysis,
- carry out network analysis and visualize a network,
- evaluate a social network using quantitative metrics,
- interpret the results of an analysis on a network

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have

- created a network and coded additional data in a format that can be recognized by common SNA software
- calculated the metrics such as degree, centrality, diversity, similarity, etc.
- clustered the vertices of the network by many different subgroup analysis

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approaches

- visualized networks and network analysis results using energy-based visualisation algorithms
- interpreted the results of analysis

COURSE OUTLINE

Introduction

- Representing networks with graphs
- Types and properties of networks
- Datasets and transformations
- Visualisation of network data
- Network manipulations
- Network generation

Sub-group analysis

- Components, cores, cliques
- Sub-group analysis for signed graphs
- Sub-group analysis for directed graphs
- Community detection
- Node similarity

Measuring social networks

- Network level metrics
- Node level metrics
- Group level metrics

Two mode networks

- Representing two-mode networks
- Two-mode to one-mode transformations

Dynamic networks

- Representing dynamic networks
- Analysing diffusion

TEXTBOOKS AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- W. de Nooy, A. Mrvar and V. Batagelj, **Exploratory Social Network Analysis using Pajek**, 3rd edition Cambridge University Press, 2018.
- Degenne and M. Forse, “Introducing social networks”, Sage Publications, London, 1999.
- H. L. Schneider and L. M. Huber, “Social Networks, Development, Evaluation and Influence, Nova Science Publishers, Inc, New York, 2008.
- M. O. Jackson, Social and Economic Networks, Princeton University Press, Princeton, New Jersey, 2008.

COURSE CONDUCT

- Lectures introducing theoretical foundations
- Hands-on practicals using Python (e.g., NetworkX, matplotlib, Pajek)
- Case studies from social, technological, biological, and information networks

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address applied knowledge of social network analysis concepts, metrics, and methods, and support learners in analyzing network structures, interpreting results, and evaluating patterns in socio-technical datasets.

INSTRUCTOR

Prof. Banu Günel Kılıç is a Professor of Information Systems specializing in signal processing, cyber security, machine learning, and social network analysis. She received her B.Sc. (Hons.) in Electrical and Electronics Engineering from Middle East Technical University (2000), an M.Sc. (Hons.) in Communication Systems and Signal Processing from the University of Bristol

(2001), and a Ph.D. in Computer Science from Queen's University Belfast (2004). Between 2004 and 2010, she worked as a Research Associate and later Senior Research Associate at the Centre for Vision, Speech and Signal Processing (CVSSP), University of Surrey, where she contributed to several EU FP6 and FP7 projects, including VISNET, VISNET-II, DIOMEDES, MUSCADE, and IRIS. Since 2010, she has been a faculty member at the Graduate School of Informatics. She is currently involved in H2020 and Digital Europe projects, including EuroCC2, EUMaster4HPC, and ACHIEVE. Her research interests include signal processing, social network analysis, multimedia systems, cyber security.

Towards HPC: from parallel algorithmics (PRAM Model) to shared memory programming (OpenMP) and distributed programming (MPI)

CATALOG DESCRIPTION

This course introduces the learner to the fundamental concepts of parallel and distributed computing, from parallel algorithmic models to the development of parallel and distributed programs intended for HPC systems. Starting with the **PRAM (Parallel Random Access Machine) model**, the learner will understand the potential and limits of parallelism and learn how to design parallel algorithms assuming an idealized parallel computing platform. Then, the learner will shift to more realistic architectures, and study how to develop parallel programs for both **shared-memory architectures** through **OpenMP** and **distributed-memory architectures** with **MPI**.

By examining both theoretical frameworks and implementation paradigms, the learner will gain insights into optimizing performance across diverse computational environments, from algorithmic design to distributed computing. Designed for professionals with foundational knowledge in computing, this course builds on intermediate-level expertise to explore advanced techniques in parallel and distributed high-performance computing.

PREREQUISITES

- Foundations of algorithms and complexity
- Notions of parallelism and concurrency in computing

COURSE OBJECTIVES

After successfully finishing the course, the students will be able to:

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- Analyze the capabilities and constraints of parallelism in computing
- Design efficient parallel algorithms to solve computational problems
- Adapt existing sequential programs into parallel implementations (using Open MP)
- Develop programs intended for distributed platforms, specifically through message-passing techniques (using MPI)

COURSE LEARNING OUTCOMES

At the end of this course, the students will have:

- Analyzed and designed parallel algorithms for classical problems such as data aggregation and data structure traversals, while assessing their efficiency
- Implemented parallel programs using OpenMP, correct in regard of potential race conditions
- Implemented distributed programs using MPI, decomposing problems into parallelizable components, ensuring proper data distribution and coordination of compute nodes

COURSE OUTLINE

Course Syllabus

Part I – PRAM: Parallel Programming in an Ideal World (10 hours)

- Introduction to PRAM (Parallel Random-Access Machine)
- PRAM models and concurrency issues (EREW, CREW, CRCW)
- Techniques for efficient parallel data processing
- Simulation and relative performance of different PRAM models
- Conclusion - Practical insights and limits of PRAM

Part II – Open MP: Parallelizing Sequential Code (6 hours)

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- Introduction to Open MP: key features, limitations, and goals
- The Fork/Join approach
- Open MP directives: pragmas and their effects
- Open MP data scoping
- Open MP thread scheduling and load balancing strategies
- Synchronization primitives - Critical sections, barriers and locks
- Open MP and reduction operations

Part III – Message Passing Interface (MPI): High-Performance Distributed Computing (8 hours)

- Distributed computing fundamentals - Shared vs. distributed memory paradigms
- Message passing basics - From sockets to MPI
- MPI: core programming model
- Point-to-Point communication in MP – Synchronous / asynchronous modes, deadlock avoidance, and practical examples
- Collective communications: barriers, broadcast, scatter, gather and reductions

TEXTBOOK AND REFERENCE MATERIALS

- H. Casanova, A. Legrand and Y. Robert. Parallel Algorithms. Chapman and Hall/CRC Press, 2008.
- J. Reif (editor). Synthesis of Parallel Algorithms. Morgan-Kaufmann, 1993.

COURSE CONDUCT

Initial Assessment: The course starts with a brief knowledge check to confirm prerequisites.

Interactive Learning: Short questions are integrated into each lecture to reinforce understanding. **Chapter Reinforcement:** Each chapter concludes with a quiz, assessing both theoretical and practical knowledge.

Hands-On Practice: Practical sessions are included within each chapter to apply learned concepts. Detailed solution walkthroughs are provided.

Automated Feedback: Coding assignments are graded automatically, offering immediate feedback.

INDICATIVE EQF ALIGNMENT

EQF 6-7: The alignment is based on the course learning outcomes, which address advanced knowledge of parallel and distributed computing models and support learners in analyzing parallelism constraints, designing efficient parallel algorithms, and implementing shared-memory and distributed solutions using OpenMP and MPI.

INSTRUCTOR

Cédric Tedeschi – Professor of Computer Science at Rennes University